

D4.7: Final dissemination report

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Ariadne is funded by the European Commission's 7th Framework Programme.

Version: 1.0 (*final*)

15th January 2017

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Document History

- 05.09.2016 – D4.7 version 0.1
- 06-01-2017 – D4.7 version 0.2
- 11-01-2017 – D4.7 version 1.0

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on dissemination activity in ARIADNE over the whole project period.

The mission of the ARIADNE is to bring together and integrate existing archaeological research data infrastructures, so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new technologies as an integral part of archaeological research methodology.

From the outset the project has aimed to raise awareness about the ARIADNE research infrastructure amongst stakeholders within the partner organisations; research institutions; managers, senior researchers, scholars, researchers and students; international networks; research infrastructures in related disciplines; policy makers and policy bodies; funding agencies including the European Commission; and the public at large.

The project:

- Identified the main channels for communication and networking with ARIADNE's stakeholder community including social media, conferences, mailing lists, etc.;
- Built a contact database;
- Participated in clustering activities with research infrastructures and related projects;
- Actively participated in national, international and domain events;
- Shared and exchanged news and information with the stakeholder community about project results, events, training and trans-national access opportunities;
- Developed a set of dissemination materials including the project website, brochures, posters and other materials.

Section 2 of this report describes networking activity including how stakeholders have been involved in the project including transnational access and training. Section 3 describes the dissemination materials and publications that have been produced. Section 4 describes the dissemination of news and information, and activity on the social networks. Section 5 summarises the large number of events (national and international) that have been organized by ARIADNE and in which the project's results have been presented by the partners. Section 6 analyses the online access to the project's website, portal and data services.

Section 7 reviews the monitoring and success indicators for the project. The project has exceeded the targets established in the initial dissemination plan:

- More than 135 different institutions have been actively involved in ARIADNE by becoming associates, participating in bi-lateral meetings, sending researchers to participate in ARIADNE TNA and training events, taking part in user surveys and other activities (the target was 100 institutions).
- At least 13,000 users have participated in events where ARIADNE's results were presented (the target was 250 individuals). Partners have participated in c. 150 international conferences presenting the project to around 4,500 researchers.
- The project website received 36,611 visitors in 53,849 sessions (the target was 12,000)

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- The ARIADNE portal received 10,819 visitors in 15,400 sessions between 1st January and 5th January 2017 (the target was 800).
- ARIADNE's social networks have 11,500 members with a reach of around 160,000 followers (the target was 15,000 members). The project newsletter has 410 subscribers (the target was 300).
- The Guides to Good practice received around 2,000 unique page views (the target was 1,500 visitors).

In December 2016, ARIADNE's results were presented in the project's final conference, which took as its theme of "Unlocking the potential of digital archaeological data". The event was well attended by project partners and representatives from key European research infrastructures for the digital humanities, from the European Archaeological Council and other key stakeholders. The conference marked the end of a highly successful project and a programme of dissemination activities in which the project's results were communicated to stakeholders by partners with passion and enthusiasm.

2 Networking activities

2.1 Consortium

The ARIADNE consortium consists of partners in sixteen countries including Sweden, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Austria, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovenia, France, the Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, Romania and Bulgaria. The partners are active in disseminating news about the project. Activities have included:

- Giving presentations at national and international events
- Organizing ARIADNE workshops at international conferences
- Distributing ARIADNE dissemination materials
- Distributing notices about ARIADNE activities to mailing lists
- Writing articles about ARIADNE activities for in-house newsletters
- Writing to individual cultural heritage institutions about the project
- Contributing articles to the ARIADNE newsletter
- Disseminating news and information about ARIADNE via the social networks
- Participating in meetings organized by research infrastructures, projects and international initiatives and giving presentations about ARIADNE and/or distributing materials
- Creating links to the ARIADNE website from the partners' own site (all partners).

2.2 Associates

ARIADNE has been actively engaging with research infrastructures and projects and has exchanged cooperation agreements with the following:

- Aarhus University, Denmark,
- Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France
- Fornleifastofnun Íslands, Reykjavík, Iceland
- Israel Antiquities Authorities, Israel
- Istituto per i Beni Artistici, Culturali, Naturali della Regione Emilia, Italy
- Soprintendenza Speciale per il Colosseo, Il Museo Nazionale Romano e l'Area Archeologica di Roma, Italy
- Dipartimenti TeSIS e di Informatica di Verona, Italy
- Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione, Italy
- Vilnius University, Lithuania
- VU University Amsterdam, Netherlands
- Museum of Cultural History at the University of Oslo, Norway
- Direção-Geral do Património Cultural, Portugal
- Universidade do Minho, Portugal
- Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, Spain
- Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Arqueología Ibérica, Spain
- Archaeological Institute of the Andalusian Heritage, Spain
- FAIMS (Federated Archaeological Information Management Systems), Australia
- Digital Antiquity, USA
- tDAR (the Digital Archaeological Record), USA

2.3 Stakeholders

The project dissemination plan (D4.2) defined the following groups amongst the ARIADNE stakeholder community:

- Internal stakeholders in the partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in archaeological research or management responsibilities relating to project activities;
- Research institutions active in the field as represented by managers and senior researchers with management duties such as deans, directors etc.;
- Scholars, researchers and students in archaeological disciplines, field archaeologists and the wider scientific community;
- International networks and research infrastructures in related disciplines;
- Policy makers and policy bodies, and funding agencies including the European Commission;
- Media and the public at large.

Throughout the project ARIADNE has worked to raise awareness of the project amongst each of these groups. This has been achieved by updating the website and tweeting regularly, the Newsletters, presenting papers and organizing workshops at national and international conferences, publishing project deliverables, presentations and other materials on SlideShare and other related dissemination activities such as poster sessions, videos on YouTube etc. The numbers of website visitors, newsletter subscribers and Twitter reach, have grown steadily throughout the project.

ARIADNE has actively engaged with **international networks** and **research infrastructures** from its launch and through out the project. DCH-RP (Digital Cultural Heritage Roadmap for Preservation), DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure), CENDARI (Collaborative European Digital Archive Infrastructure) and the European Association of Archaeologists were involved in the ARIADNE's launch event. DARIAH, CENDARI and CLARIN (Language Studies) all participated in the Research Infrastructures conference in Rome in 2014. The projects regularly exchange news and support each other's dissemination activities.

2.4 Special Interest Groups

Special Interest Groups were established by work package 2 for project partners and external experts with an interest in:

- 3D and Visualisation
- Archaeological Research Practices and Methods
- Remote Sensing and Spatial Data
- Scientific Data
- Excavation and Monument Data

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- Grey Literature
- Metadata and Semantics
- Linked Data

These groups met, in person and virtually, surveying the state-of-the-art in their field, exchanged information, identified issues and planned future activities. A section of the ARIADNE project website has been set up to hold information about the Special Interest Groups:

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Community/Special-Interest-Groups>.

ARIADNE

English
Register Login

About Portal Transnational Access Community Events Resources News

Ariadne > Community > Special Interest Groups

Special Interest Groups

There are eight Special Interest Groups (SIGs) which each address a specific topic for further investigation and research within ARIADNE.

Each SIG has the following objectives:

- To survey the state of the art of research on their specific theme with a focus on issues concerning the creation and use of related datasets, availability of open-source tools, FAQs, etc.
- To produce focused input for the Users' Needs Report and the Innovation Agenda (medium and long-term scenarios for the impact of ARIADNE on the archaeological research framework and methodologies),
- To contribute to the analysis of the outcomes of the User Needs Survey e.g. how the available dataset infrastructure supports research on a specific theme (e.g. dendrochronology) and which are the related existing or unsatisfied needs,
- To provide input to the project repository concerning software to be stored and/or linked to,
- To provide directions for training and to suggest good practices in the relevant field, leading to the publication of specific "Guides".

Associate members are very welcome to join the SIGs – please contact the relevant Co-ordinator to be registered as a member and to be included in the discussions.

1. [3D & Visualization](#)
2. [Archaeological Research Practices & Methods](#)
3. [Remote Sensing & Spatial Data](#)
4. [Scientific Data](#)
5. [Excavation & Monument Data](#)
6. [Grey Literature](#)
7. [Linked Data](#)
8. [Semantics & Metadata](#)

Associated partners
Associated projects
Special Interest Groups
3D and Visualization
Archaeological Research Practices and Methods
Remote Sensing & Spatial Data
Scientific Data
Excavation and Monument Data
Grey Literature
Linked Data
Semantics & Metadata
Links
Share | Facebook | LinkedIn | Google+ | Twitter

2.5 Trans national access for researchers

ARIADNE has offered a range of opportunities to researchers under its transnational access programme including training events, access visits and summer schools, these are reported in detail in D5.1. A range of dissemination activities have been carried out to promote these opportunities including news articles on the project website and in the project newsletters, tweets to advertise calls for applications, publication of training materials via Slideshare and so on.

2.5.1 Training events

During the project the following events took place:

- Two TNA training workshops were organized to provide an introduction to online services for archaeology datasets:
 - EAA Pilsen, September 2013 (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/EAA-2013-Workshop>)
 - CAA Paris, April 2014 (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/ARIADNE-workshop-CAA2014-Paris>)
- Three TNA workshops were organized to provide an introduction to the opportunities for TNA access visits:
 - EVA London, July 2014 (see <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/TNA-Workshop-EVA-2014>)
 - EAA Istanbul, September 2014 (see <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Media/Files/EAA-2014-Open-Access-Session-Report>)
 - MEAT Paestum, October 2014
- Conference session on the theme of “Supporting researchers in the use and reuse of archaeological data: following the ARIADNE thread” were organized at
 - CAA Siena, March 2015 (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/Archaeological-data-CAA2015>)
 - CAA Oslo, March 2016 (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/CAA-2016-Session>)
 - EAA Vilnius, September 2016 (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/EAA-2016-Session>)
- A training event on 3DHOP was organized at the Digital Heritage Conference in Granada, September 2015 (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/3D-HOP-Digital-Heritage-2015>)
- Expert forum on the future of archaeological knowledge were organized by the Digital Curation Unit in Athens in July 2015 and again in June 2016.
- Two training events on the management of archaeological datasets were organized (the training materials are available here: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Transnational-Access/Training-Materials>) :
 - Data Management Workshop, Vienna, Jan 2016
 - Data Management Workshop, Ljubljana, Jan 2016.

2.5.2 Access visits

Physical access to ARIADNE TNA services was launched in summer 2014 with 3 inaugural summer schools on 3D Documentation, the CIDOC-CRM and design of Archaeological Datasets taking place. The programme of access visits continued in 2015 and 2016 with researchers participating in TNA at PIN, CNR- ISTI and Athena RC. Each year there have been rolling calls for applications for access visits advertised internationally to researchers and advanced-level students via the project website, mailing lists and the social media.

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ARIADNE Transnational Access (TNA) visits included:

- Mapping existing datasets to the CIDOC CRM; individual training at PIN
- 2D/3D documentation for archaeology, 22-26 June 2015, CNR-ISTI
- Design of archaeological datasets, 6-10 July 2015, CNR-ISTI
- Design of archaeological datasets, 28 June-3 July 2015, Athena-RC Athens
- Digital curation of archaeological knowledge, 12-17 June 2016, Athena-RC Athens
- 2D/3D documentation for archaeology, 20-24 June 2016, CNR-ISTI.
- Design of archaeological datasets, 4-8 July 2016, CNR-ISTI
- Interoperability of archaeological datasets, 12-14 December 2016, PIN

The calls for participation were advertised on the project website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Transnational-Access> and disseminated via the social media and the project newsletter.

Flyers were produced to advertise the calls for participation at conferences and events.

News items about the events were published on the project website. For example:

- Feedback from one researcher, Roberta Zeni, who visited PIN in Prato for TNA on mapping legacy data to the CIDOC CRM was reported on the ARIADNE website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/Interview-with-Roberta-Zeni-on-Mapping-EpiDoc-to-CIDOC-CRM>
- A short article about the work of Ivana Posedi in applying the CIDOC-CRM to her archaeological science dataset on the provenance of stained glass windows: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/CIDOC-CRM-and-the-Provenance-of-Stained-Glass-Windows>
- A short article about the ARIADNE winter school: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/ARIADNE-winter-school>
- A blog-post about TNA training on the applicability of the CIDOC-CRM <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/TNA-Training-demonstrates-the-wide-applicability-of-CIDOC-CRM>
- News items about the TNA on 3D documentation for archaeology datasets: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/3D-summer-school-2016>

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for About, Portal, Transnational Access, Community, Events, Resources, and News. Below the menu, the breadcrumb trail reads 'Ariadne > News > ARIADNE winter school'. The main heading is 'ARIADNE winter school' with a sub-heading 'Wed 14 Dec 2016'. A photograph shows a group of people in a meeting room. The text describes a winter school where researchers met to discuss interoperability of archaeological datasets. A sidebar on the right contains links for 'Partner reports', 'Media reports about us', 'ARIADNE newsletter', and 'Press', along with social media sharing options for Google+, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter.

2.6 Other activities

ARIADNE has taken part in a range of other networking activities during the project including:

Conference session on "Infrastructures & services for sharing of archaeological documentation" at the Cultural Heritage and New Technologies conference (CHNT 2013) in Vienna in November 2013.

Conference sessions on Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology at EAA 2014 and the 8th German Archaeological congress, which were both well attended. These sessions were organized by Frank Siegmund (Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf), Julian D. Richards (Archaeology Data Service) and Guntram Geser (Salzburg Research) and resulted in a journal publication: **Archäologische Informationen in Band 38: Fokus: Open Access & Open Data**. <http://journals.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/index.php/arch-inf/issue/view/2578/showToc>

Save the data – workshop on digital repositories organized by OEAW in collaboration with the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities in December 2014. See <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/Save-the-data>

Round table on long-term preservation and access to archaeological data at the Cultural Heritage and New Technologies conference (CHNT 2016) held in Vienna in November 2016. The round table was organized by Edeltraud Aspöck (OEAW) and Guntram Geser (Salzburg Research) and was attended by around twenty experts in the field of curating, preserving and disseminating digital data within archaeology.

Collaboration with Perio.do, a gazetteer of scholarly definitions of historical, art-historical, and archaeological periods, to publish chronologies of European and Mediterranean archaeology as Linked Open Data (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/PeriodO>).

3 Materials and publications

3.1 Dissemination materials

A set of dissemination materials was established for use by project partners including the project logo, project website, templates for presentations and documents, a project poster and project leaflets.

The project has produced posters, leaflets and flyers during the lifetime of the project. The flyer illustrated below was produced to advertise the new ARIADNE services and the call for applications for TNA at the CAA conference in Spring 2016.

ARIADNE
2016 TNA: call for applications

Researchers are invited to apply to participate in Summer Schools and/or individual training visits. Your own research forms an important part of both the summer schools and individual training where you will develop your case studies or research projects under expert supervision. We welcome applications from individuals with a scientific interest and ability to benefit from training in archaeological research data management.

ARIADNE is a project funded by the European Commission under the Community's Seventh Framework Programme

Sponsorship is available up to 1000 Euro participant (to cover the cost of travel and accommodation) plus a tuition fee waiver. Bursaries are awarded on a competitive basis, according to the procedure described in the application pack and eligibility criteria above, and based upon the quality of the applicant, their proposed project, and their personal statement. 3-10 bursaries are available from ARIADNE in 2016 for each TNA centre listed above.

For more information and details on how to apply visit:
www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Services/Transnational-Access/2016-TNA-Call

First 2016 call is open until 29 April 2016

ARIADNE Services

ARIADNE services will be available through a state of the art portal for the archaeology research community.

ARIADNE Registry

The ARIADNE Registry integrates information from archaeological research institutions across Europe. The ARIADNE Catalog Data Model forms the basis for integration and normalizing metadata records. MoRe's micro-service oriented architecture provides the platform for enriching and storing all the information in RDF (and, soon, in CRM) format as well as the Elasticsearch engine that powers the ARIADNE portal.

info@ariadne-infrastructure.eu

Visual Media Service

ARIADNE's Visual Media Service provides easy publication and presentation on the web of complex visual media assets. 3D models, RTI images and high-resolution images can be uploaded on ARIADNE's server and automatically transformed into efficient web formats, making them ready for visualisation online.

visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

The ARIADNE Portal

A central point of access to a large and growing amount of information on archaeological resources from across Europe. The portal's Elasticsearch engine allows researchers to browse the Catalog by region, period and subject (where, when and what). The portal will offer access to more than a million archaeological datasets being collected through the ARIADNE project.

portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

Landscape Services

A set of responsive web and cloud services to process, manage and share DEM, geo-images and shape files to produce large terrain datasets optimized for real-time visualisation and web-streaming.

landscape.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

3.1.1 Project website

The ARIADNE website (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>) was launched in month one of the project. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and to related projects. The public part of the website includes:

- About - the project, consortium and activities
- Services – Trans National Access, Online Services, Training opportunities
- Community – joining the network, special interest groups, associated projects
- Events calendar
- Resources – presentations, publications, links and other useful resources
- News – news stories, bulletins and newsletter

Throughout the project the website has been maintained and developed with new sections and new content being added as the project’s activities have advanced. For example, the Services page had new sub-folders added for software tools made available to the project.

The website is available in English.

Project resources are published on the ARIADNE website in a dedicated section:

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

This section includes information about:

- The Ariadne Catalogue Data Model
- Mappings to the Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) completed by ARIADNE partners
- Contribution to Perio.do by ARIADNE partners
- Information about the ARIADNE services
- Project deliverables and publications

3.1.2 Project leaflet

MiBACT-ICCU coordinated the preparation of two project leaflets. The first was produced in summer 2013 and was distributed by partners at a series of events. An updated version of the leaflet was produced in autumn 2016 (see below).

3.1.3 ARIADNE Booklets

A booklet was produced and first distributed at the Infrastructures event in Rome in November 2014. This proved to be very popular and has been one of the most downloaded of the project documents included in the project SlideShare.

A second booklet was produced for distribution at the final project event in Firenze in December 2016. This booklet provides an overview and introduction to the project's results, ARIADNE content and services, special achievements such as the project's contribution to standards and the training that has been offered to archaeological researchers.

ARIADNE

All fields ▾ Search for resources in the Ariadne catalog ...

Welcome

ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology.

Browse the Catalog

Where [Map of Europe]

When [Bar chart showing data distribution]

What [Word cloud]

Word cloud terms: farms, houses, churches (buildings), farmhouses, ditches, low kilns, stone, iron, churchyards, remains, unexcavated, kerbs, forts.

Building a research infrastructure for Digital Archaeology in Europe

3.1 Guides to Good Practice and Case studies

A series of Guides to Good Practice and case studies have been published during the project.

The first case study, published in 2013, was produced by Felix Schäfer of the Deutsches Archäologisches Institut on the “Selection and Retention of Files in Big Data Collections: The Example of the Pergamon Excavation of the DAI Istanbul”. The case study is available from: http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/CS_ARIADNE-DAI-Schafer.

News about the case study was reported on the ARIADNE website and via Twitter.

Since this first case study the following guides have been published by ARIADNE:

- Dendrochronological Data in Archaeology: A Guide to Good Practice:
http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Dendro_Toc
- 3D Models in Archaeology: A Guide to Good Practice:
http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/3d_Toc
- Case study: the Dendrochronology of the Early Medieval Emporium Dorestad, the Netherlands: http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Dendro_CS
- Thermoluminescence dating: A guide to Good practice:
http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/TL_Toc

Web access statistics available from the ADS reveal that:

- The case study ‘Selection and Retention of Files in Big Data Collections: The Example of the Pergamon Excavation of the DAI Istanbul’ has had **348 unique page views**, with an average time spent per visit on the page of **1 minute 13 seconds**. This is very favourable comparable to other Guides to Good practice case studies.
- The Dendrochronology Guide to Good Practice has had **1275 unique page views**
- The case study “Dendrochronology of the Early Medieval Emporium Dorestad (added in June 2016) has had **50 unique page views**.
- The 3D Models Guide to Good Practice has had **409 unique page views** since December 2016.

3.2 Publications

ARIADNE partners have published 85 project-related articles in journals, conference proceedings, books and other publications. This number includes one major forthcoming publication on the ARIADNE data infrastructure and services. This paper will appear in a special issue of the Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage on research infrastructures, edited by leading researchers of the ARIADNE project.

Forthcoming

Meghini C., Scopigno R., Richards J., Geser G. *et al.* (2017): ARIADNE: A Research Infrastructure for Archaeology. In: Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage, Vol. 10, Issue 1, January 2017 (forthcoming).

2016

Aloia N., Debole F. & Meghini C. (2016): Un Catalogo per la Descrizione di Risorse Archeologiche, pp. 26-35, in: Ronzino P. (ed., 2016): L’integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia (InDARD-2015). Proceedings del Workshop, Lecce, Italia, 1-2 Ottobre 2015, <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1634/paper4.pdf>

Binding, C. and D. Tudhope (2016) "Improving interoperability using vocabulary linked data", *International Journal on Digital Libraries*, Volume 17, issue 1, March 2016, pp. 5-21, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00799-015-0166-y>

Brewer P. & Jansma E. (2016): The Dendrochronology of the Early-medieval Emporium Dorestad, Netherlands (Case study, July 2016). In: *Archaeology Data Service & Digital Antiquity: Guides to Good Practice*, http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Dendro_CS

Di Giorgio S., Felicetti A., Martini P. & Masci E. (2016): Dati.CulturaItalia: a Use Case of Publishing Linked Open Data Based on CIDOC-CRM, pp. 44-54, in: Ronzino P. (ed.): *Extending, Mapping and Focusing the CRM. Proceedings of the EMF-CRM workshop at the 19th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2015)*, Poznan, Poland, 17 September 2015, <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1656/paper4.pdf>

Di Giorgio, Sara (2016): Gli Archivi del MiBACT. L'Integrazione dei Dati Archeologici Digitali, pp. 47-55, in: Ronzino P. (ed., 2016): *L'integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia (InDARD-2015)*. Proceedings del Workshop, Lecce, Italia, 1-2 Ottobre 2015, <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1634/paper6.pdf>

Doerr, M., Theodoridou, M., Aspöck, E. and A. Masur (2016) "Mapping archaeological databases to CIDOC-CRM" in *CAA 2015 Keep the Revolution Going: Proceedings of the 43rd Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology* (eds. S Campana, R. Scopigno, G. Carpentiero and M. Cirillo) vol.1, Archeopress, p.p.443-452, <http://archaeopress.com/ArchaeopressShop/Public/download.asp?id={77DEDD4E-DE8F-43A4-B115-ABE0BB038DA7}>

Felicetti, A. (2016) "L'infrastruttura di integrazione in ARIADNE", in P. Ronzino, (ed.): *L'integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia (InDARD-2015)*, Proceedings del Workshop, Lecce, Italia, 1-2 Ottobre 2015, <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1634/paper3.pdf>.

Felicetti A. and F. Murano (2016) "Scripta Manent. A CIDOC CRM Semiotic Reading of Ancient Texts", *International Journal of Digital Libraries*, online 22 July 2016, <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00799-016-0189-z>

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4 Information and news

The project has disseminated information and news about the project's activities and related areas via the project website, a project newsletter, social media channels and (to a more limited extent) to the press.

Throughout the project news content has been added to the website, which includes regular news items, partner reports (e.g. about Conferences or workshops), media reports, the newsletters and press (Press releases and other information aimed at the press).

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website's news section. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for About, Services, Community, Events, Resources, and News. The main content area features three news items:

- ARIADNE at CAA2016** (12 Feb 16): Continuing the discussion that began at last year's CAA, ARIADNE has organised a session which will be held at CAA2016 in Oslo on Wednesday 30th March.
- CAA Recycle Award** (9 Feb 16): CAA is launching an annual Recycle Award to recognize those who breathe new life into old data. The award will be presented jointly to the best example of data re-use presented at the CAA International Conference and the project or institution that made the data available.
- Data in libraries - Call for papers (IFLA)** (26 Jan 16): IFLA World Library and Information Congress, 82nd IFLA General Conference and Assembly, 13-19 August 2016, Columbus, Ohio, United States of America.

On the right side, there is a sidebar with links for Partner reports, Media reports about us, ARIADNE newsletter, and Press. Below these links are social media sharing icons for Share, Facebook, LinkedIn, Google+, and Twitter.

The main section is used to publish short news articles and announcements (such as calls for papers and participation in events): <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News>. In addition, news posted on the project's Twitter account is published on the home page of the project's website.

4.1 Project newsletter

ARIADNE produces periodic newsletters highlighting activities by the project (events, publications, new releases), partner activities and activities by partner projects such as DARIAH, SENESCHAL and the ARCHES project. Issues were published in:

- July 2013
- February 2014
- July 2014
- November 2014
- May 2015
- October 2015
- February 2016
- July 2016
- November 2016

Each issue of the newsletter has highlighted activities by ARIADNE, partner activities and related projects and initiatives such as the Open Access Repository Ranking and the Linked Pasts event.

The newsletter is distributed directly to stakeholders who have registered to be on our mailing list and indirectly via notices to mailing lists and on Twitter. The project mailing list has grown steadily throughout the project, with 410 subscribers now being registered. The most recent edition, which included an invitation to the ARIADNE conference, had a 53% open rate with 37 click-throughs to the website.

The newsletters are available from the project website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/Newsletters>.

4.2 Press

ARIADNE events and results have been reported in the media, social media and blogs from across Europe.

A press release was prepared for the project launch (see: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News/ARIADNE-Press-release-17042013>) and circulated by the project partners. The **project launch** itself was reported in La Stampa. *Nasce Ariadne e l'archeologia diventa una e-science.*

The **event on Research Infrastructures on Cultural Heritage in Rome in November 2014**, which was organized by ARIADNE and MIBACT, in the framework of the Italian EU Presidency was widely reported in the Italian media and internationally:

- La Repubblica, November 16th, 2014. *Un Google dedicato all'archeologia. Lo vuole l'Uell progetto.*
- Il Sole 24 Ora. *Conferenza su infrastrutture di ricerca e infrastrutture digitali per il patrimonio culturale.*
- Cultura Italia article. *Infrastrutture digitali, dai beni culturali enormi moli di dati per la ricerca.*
- Cultura Italia interview with Franco Niccolucci. *"Ariadne, un super Google dell'archeologia, ma più intelligente".*
- Penguino. *L'archeologia diventa moderna con il progetto ARIADNE.*
- Stella Nova article. *ARIADNE, L'Archeologia a Portata di Mouse.*
- ADNKronos, October 18th, 2014. Beni culturali: a Roma brainstorming su Infrastrutture digitali e di ricerca
- AISE – Agenzia Internazionale Stampa Estero, November 9th, 2014 Alla Biblioteca Nazionale di Roma la conferenza "Infrastrutture di ricerca e digitali per il patrimonio culturale"
- ArtEconomy24 – Il Sole 24 Ore, November 13th, 2014 Conferenza su infrastrutture di ricerca e infrastrutture digitali per il patrimonio culturale
- La Stampa, November 17th, 2014, L'archeologia europea a portata di clic
- IncontraGiovani, November 13th, 2014 Infrastrutture di ricerca e digitali per il patrimonio culturale
- Europa Facile, November 4th, 2014 Conferenza internazionale "Infrastrutture di ricerca e digitali per il patrimonio culturale"
- Archeomatica, October 24th, 2014 Workshop internazionale sull'Infrastruttura di ricerca archeologica del progetto ARIADNE
- Corriere delle Comunicazioni *Conferenza internazionale infrastrutture di ricerca e infrastrutture digitali per il patrimonio culturale*
- Cultura e Innovazione Workshop internazionale sull'Infrastruttura di ricerca archeologica del progetto ARIADNE
- Sistema Bibliotecario della Provincia di Roma Conferenza su infrastrutture di ricerca e infrastrutture digitali per il patrimonio culturale
- Tafter, November 25th, 2014 ARIADNE, l'archeologia europea online
- Madata. Βόλτα στην Αμφίπολη με ένα κλικ στο Google Map. [Walk in Amphipolis with a click on Google Maps].
- News Now Greek. Βόλτα στην Αμφίπολη με ένα κλικ στο Google Map.

- Espressonews.gr, November 18th, 2014 Με ένα «κλικ» στο Google map «πας» Αμφίπολη
- TV: Interview of Rossella Caffo and Franco Niccolucci by RAI CULTURA. *Le infrastrutture digitali al servizio dei beni culturali.*
- TV: Interview with Franco Niccolucci and feature by ADNkronos. *Inizia l'era dell'archeologia 2.0.*
- Radio: GR2 interview with Franco Niccolucci.
- Radio 24 interview with Franco Niccolucci.
- TAZ.DE Datenbanken für Archäologen: <http://www.taz.de/!144567/>
- APA Europäische Grabungsdatenbank nimmt Gestalt an: https://science.apa.at/dossier/Europaeische_Grabungsdatenbank_nimmt_Gestalt_an/

More recently, the **ARIADNE session at EAA 2016** was reported in a paper by Dr. Jean-Olivier Gransard-Desmond in the *Archéologia* magazine. The magazine is for a general audience interested in archaeology in France including students, archaeologists and volunteers. The paper: “Sur le terrain: 22e Rencontre de l'European Association of Archaeologists”, *Archéologia* 548, éd. Faton, novembre 2016, Dijon, p. 14-15. Dr. Gransard-Desmond wrote

Sur le terrain

VILNIUS
22^e RENCONTRE DE L'EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF ARCHAEOLOGISTS

La Rencontre annuelle de l'European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) organisée à Vilnius du 31 août au 4 septembre 2016 est une occasion de découvrir cette ONG qui représente la communauté archéologique européenne auprès des instances européennes.

QUE FAIT L'EAA ?
Par le nombre de ses membres, la qualité de son organisation et une volonté d'associer à une pratique professionnelle une dimension responsable et éthique, l'EAA s'est assurée un siège au Conseil de l'Europe en 1999. Sa voix consultative a été transformée en 2003 en voie participative lors de la modification des statuts des ONG siégeant au Conseil de l'Europe. L'EAA est ainsi en capacité d'influencer la politique européenne en matière de recherche archéologique et de défense du patrimoine, ce qui la rend d'autant plus précieuse au sein de la communauté archéologique européenne. Afin de faciliter la liaison entre ses membres et le reste de la communauté archéologique, l'EAA dispose d'un organe de communication scientifique avec la revue à comité de lecture *European Journal of Archaeology* (EJA) et d'un organe d'actualités avec *The European Archaeologist* (TEA). Elle organise également chaque année une rencontre dans une ville européenne différente : l'Annual Meeting.

L'ANNUAL MEETING DE VILNIUS
Cette année, plus de 1400 communications et posters ont été présentés lors des 98 sessions, 7 tables rondes et 5 rencontres de comités ou ateliers. Sur 1394 participants, 63 représentaient la France. Si une majorité d'entre eux provenait du CNRS et de l'université, l'Inrap, les collectivités, le ministère de la Culture ainsi qu'une entreprise et une association ont également fait le déplacement.

Le Dr. Felipe Criado-Boado, actuel président de l'EAA. ©IC: Zakaruskaitė, 2016

Malgré ses 1780 membres, ses 22 années d'existence et ses 13 groupes de travail sur des sujets touchant autant à la recherche scientifique en archéologie qu'au management et à la veille sur cette recherche, l'EAA fait encore peu parler d'elle. Présidée par le Dr. Felipe Criado-Boado de l'Instituto de Ciencias del Patrimonio (Espagne), elle serait pourtant la seconde association de professionnels et de bénévoles de l'archéologie et du patrimoine la plus importante au monde après la Society for American Archaeology.

Le portail ARIADNE. Un accès ouvert aux données archéologiques respectueux des questions légales et de l'intégrité des bases de données des laboratoires. ©Actiade

“Quant aux groupes de travail externes, 2016 fut l'occasion pour les partenaires du projet européen ARIADNE d'une présentation special destinée à faire un état des lieux des résultats de l'année. En effet, l'objectif d'ARIADNE est d'intégrer l'infrastructure des données archéologiques des laboratoires européens partenaires pour la diffusion des dites données auprès des scientifiques du monde entier afin de faciliter l'exploration de nouvelles méthodologies de recherche. Cette session a permis de montrer la variété des initiatives destinées à l'ouverture des données archéologiques dont le portail ARIADNE est un exemple.”

In addition, the online magazine “Digital Meets Culture” has advertised ARIADNE events and reported on events and the memorandum of understanding that was exchanged with the DCH-RP project.

Join the Digital Meets Culture Open Newsroom!

If you have interesting news and events to point out in the field of digital cultural heritage, we are waiting for your contribution.

[Join](#)

Free text [search](#)

Search Results for: ariadne

On 9th January 2014 a Memorandum of Understanding has been signed between the two projects

MoU between DCH-RP and ARIADNE

Aim of the agreement is to promote and support scientific collaboration between the Archaeological research Infrastructures and DCH-RP partners in order to share knowledge in the sector of digital preservation of DCH and to cooperate to the dissemination of the projects' results. [Continue reading](#) →

ARIADNE Florence (Italy), 15-16 December 2016

Unlocking the Potential of Digital Archaeological Data – ARIADNE Final Conference

The ARIADNE Research Infrastructure final conference "Unlocking the Potential of Digital Archaeological Data" will be held in the beautiful Sala Luca Giordano in the Palazzo Medici Riccardi, Florence, Italy on Thursday 15th to Friday 16th December 2016. The Conference will ... [Continue reading](#) →

NEWSLETTERS

Situ Xiaochun Art Space

DIGITAL HERITAGE SHOWCASES

E|SPACE

4.3 Social networks

4.3.1 Twitter

@Ariadne_Network was established on Twitter in April 2013. By 31st December 2016, activity had more than doubled from the first 18-month period:

- 754 followers (up 250 from 31st December 2015)
- @Ariadne_Network is following 361 Twitter users
- @Ariadne_Network had made 1,882 Tweets since the start of the project, 772 during 2016.

The graph (from <http://www.twitonomy.com/>) for the date range 18 April 2013 to 04 Jan 2017 shows a fairly consistent level Twitter activity from the second quarter of 2014 on. There were peaks in activity during the Infrastructure conference in November 2014, during CAA in April 2015 and again in April 2016, during EAA and the final project conference in December 2016 Italy.

The statistics reveal:

- an average of 1.39 tweets per day
- 26% of ARIADNE tweets were retweeted; 443 tweets were retweeted a total of 1,140 times
- 18% of ARIADNE tweets were favourited; 334 tweets were favourited

The users most re-tweeted by ARIADNE were:

@DigCurationUnit 30	@Julian62523002 27
@IntarchEditor 26	@DARIAHeu 25
@DiscProg 21	@3DIcons 19
@OpenAccessArch 19	@ADS_Update 19
@britishmuseum 17	@VAST_LAB 17

The top 10 Re-tweets shows there was a high level of interest in papers for international conferences, ARIADNE training opportunities, open access to research data and technologies.

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Rank	Subject matter	No. of retweets	Date
1	Call for papers on digital infrastructures for cultural heritage	22	26 Nov 2015
2	Flyer with details of ARIADNE TNA opportunities	20	13 April 2016
3	Launch of ARIADNE survey on access to research data	15	21 Nov 2013
4	Technologies used by @Fastionline	12	30 Mar 2016
5	Cool opportunity: summer school on digital curation of archaeological knowledge	12	22 Apr 2016

The most favoured tweets confirm the interest in ARIADNE presentations published on Slideshare and in open data.

Rank	Subject matter	No. of favourites	Date
1	Linked Open Data Approaches, Holly Wright – presentation on Slideshare	11	5 Sep 2016
2	Call for papers on Digital Infrastructures for Cultural heritage	8	26 Nov 2015
3	We need success stories to demonstrate to people that open data really works – looking forwards to hearing yours	7	1 Sep 2016
4	Technologies used by @Fastionline	6	30 Mar 2016
5	Requirements for Open Sharing of Research data, presentation by Guntram Geser via Slideshare	6	2 Sep 2016

ARIADNE has been mentioned 787 times throughout the project by 170 users on average 0.7 times per day. The graph of mentions below shows the pattern of mentions and the increase in activity during key events including conferences and workshops.

The 170 users who have mentioned ARIADNE have a very large potential reach with an aggregated total of 1.6 million followers (a conservative estimate of the number of unique twitter users might be 10% of this aggregated figure or 160,000). The most influential users who follow ARIADNE are:

- @TIM_Official 487,621 followers
- @Social_Quant_Geni 31,783 followers
- @acropolita 27,981 followers
- @archaeologyUK 25,719 followers
- @HuttonPulitzer

The most active users following, mentioning, retweeting and favouriting ARIADNE are:

- @DigCurationUnit 668 followers
- @Julian62523002 1763 followers
- @VAST_LAB 115 followers
- @diggingitall 321 followers
- @costisd 1059 followers
- @ADS_Update 4506 followers
- @agiati 1181 followers
- @ADS_Chatter 749 followers
- @claudiam829 355 followers

4.3.2 LinkedIn

A LinkedIn Group has been set up for the ARIADNE Network and currently has 39 members. The group has been relatively inactive as Twitter and SlideShare are more popular social media channels with ARIADNE.

Number of members: 39

Number of discussions: 29

4.3.3 Facebook

A Facebook group was established for ARIADNE in May 2015. The group has been used to post news and photographs from ARIADNE events.

Number of members: 21

4.3.4 SlideShare

A SlideShare account was set up for ARIADNE in July 2014. By January 2017, 91 presentations and 27 documents had been uploaded and there had been a total of 69,270 views. ARIADNE has 11 followers on Slideshare.

Over the last twelve months there have been a total of 36,165 views (a 45% increase since the previous year when there were 25,751 views). The graph shows that there was increased activity on SlideShare during February 2016 following the publication of training materials from the Data Management training workshops in Vienna and Ljubljana; and also in September 2016 following the publication of slides from the ARIADNE workshop at EAA.

The top viewed content over the twelve months from January 2016 was the 2014 ARIADNE booklet (3055 views), the ARIADNE report on Linked data and Natural Language Processing (1198 views) and presentations on Archiving Archaeological data in Austria (764 views), the ARIADNE project (759 views) and ARIADNE services (725 views). The top countries for viewers were United States, United Kingdom, Germany, France and Italy.

Overall, since the SlideShare account was launched the 20 most popular documents and presentations are shown in the table below – the statistics reveal that views build up over time and thus the most popular documents were uploaded in 2013 and 2014.

Ariadne Booklet: The Way Forward to Digital Archaeology in Europe (2014)	6483
ARIADNE introduction (2013 presentation)	3523
ARIADNE: First report on users' needs (2014)	2089
The ARIADNE project (2014 presentation)	1590
Open Data in Archaeology (2014 presentation)	1586

Identify criteria and fundamental concepts in archaeology: the case of the archaeological site (2014 presentation)	1505
A first attempt at describing, disseminating and reusing methodological knowledge in Archaeology (2014 presentation)	1485
Austrian archaeological data and archiving options (2015 presentation)	1446
ARIADNE overview (2014 presentation)	1412
ARIADNE: Report on project standards	1372
ARIADNE update (2014 presentation)	1370
Integrating archaeological data: the ARIADNE infrastructure (2015 presentation)	1356
Open Access in Italy (2014 presentation)	1211
Open Access of Research Data: the present and future situation in Germany (2014 presentation)	1173
“Archäologische Informationen” and Open Journal Systems. Chances and Possibilities of an Open Access Journal (2014 presentation)	1113
ARIADNE: First report on natural language processing	998
The Geographic Archaeological Information system of Rome: between IPR and privacy protection law (presentation)	949
Barriers and opportunities: Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology (2014 presentation)	917
Think big about data: Archaeology and the big data challenge (2014 presentation)	912
Open Data Publication: requirements, good practices and benefits (2014 presentation)	882

Although the earliest of ARIADNE’s uploads have attracted the most views, recent uploads of presentations from the conference in Florence in December 2016 have each attracted around 50 views in a two-day period.

YouTube

Although no project account was created on YouTube, a number of ARIADNE related videos have been uploaded:

PIN uploaded a presentation of the ARIADNE project given at the 'kick-off' conference in Rome in February 7, 2013; this short video has had 48 viewings. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9x1-4Ddux8E>.

Franco Niccolucci (PIN) gave a **presentation about ARIADNE at the event “Fostering the Transatlantic Dialogue on Digital Heritage & EU Research Infrastructure”** at the Library of Congress, Washington, US in March 2015. (1:08 – 1:26). This has had 94 views. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PUKgu6dSvMM>

Bruno Fanini (CNR-ISTI) uploaded a short video about the ARIADNE Landscape service in April 2016, which had had 51 views. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=45VIGg7HLcc>

ARIADNE Landscape Services 2016

Bruno Fanini

8 months ago • 51 views

ARIADNE Landscape Services <http://landscape.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/> Developed by VHLab, CNR ITABC ...

5 Events

Partners have participated in over 210 conferences, workshops and other events during the four years of the project. There were 67 events organized by ARIADNE partners (including conference sessions, workshops, round tables and meetings) attended by approximately 3,000 researchers. In addition to these events, partners presented ARIADNE at around 150 events attended by approximately 9,500 researchers. Around 20 short training courses and hands-on workshops in which approximately 500 researchers participated were organized during the four years of the project.

5.1 International events

The ARIADNE session on Open Access in Archaeology, EAA 2016 Vilnius.

The full list of activities is presented in Annex 2, a few highlights are:

- **Preservation and re-use of digital archaeological research data with open archival information systems**, conference session and round table, CHNT 2016, Vienna, Austria
- **Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology: Following the ARIADNE thread**, conference session, EAA 2016, Vilnius, Lithuania
- **Supporting Users in the Use and Re-Use of Archaeological Data**, conference session, CAA 2016, Oslo, Norway
- **Extending, Mapping and Focusing the CRM**, workshop, TPD 2015, Poznan, Poland

- **Supporting Users in the Use and Re-Use of Archaeological Data**, conference session, CAA, April, 2015, Siena, Italy.
- **Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures for Cultural Heritage**, ARIADNE conference, November 2014, Rome, Italy

Figure: The Open Access session at EAA 2015, Istanbul.

- **Open Access and Open Data as steps towards Open Archaeology**, conference session, EAA 2014, Istanbul, Turkey
- **Online Resources for Archaeological Research**, workshop, CAA 2014, Paris, France
- **Infrastructures and Services for the sharing of archaeological documentation**, session, CHNT 2013, Vienna, Austria
- **Practical Experiences with CIDOC CRM and its Extensions (CRMEX)** – three ARIADNE papers were presented in this workshop, TPDL 2013, Valetta, Malta
- **New Digital Developments in Heritage Management and Research**, conference session, EAA 2013, Pilsen, Czech Republic
- **Data Management Planning and Online Resources for Archaeology**, pre-conference workshop, EAA 2013, Pilsen, Czech Republic

FASTI Online was recognized by the Archaeological Institute of America, receiving an award for “outstanding work in digital archaeology” in January 2014; the presentation of the award provided an opportunity for AIAC to speak about both FASTI Online and ARIADNE to the members of the Institute.

PIN has had regular meetings with research infrastructures, projects and research institutions to discuss opportunities for collaboration. ARIADNE is an affiliated project of DARIAH (the digital research infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) and regularly exchanges news and participates in events.

The screenshot shows the top part of the DARIAH-EU website. At the top left is the DARIAH-EU logo, a stylized blue flower-like shape, followed by the text "DARIAH-EU | Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities". Below this is a navigation bar with five orange buttons: "About", "What we do", "Contributions", "News", and "Service". To the right of the navigation bar is a breadcrumb trail: "Home / About / Affiliated projects / ARIADNE". Below the navigation bar, the word "ARIADNE" is written in large, bold, blue letters. To the right of this is a smaller logo for ARIADNE, which consists of a stylized orange and blue grid icon followed by the word "ARIADNE" in orange. Below the main heading, there is a paragraph of text: "ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology."

ARIADNE is an affiliated project of DARIAH

Franco Niccolucci was also invited to present the project at the European Research Infrastructure event organized at the Library of Congress, Washington, US and then at Cultura Patrimonia, Mexico in December 2014. Other partners have been to Valparaíso, Chile and San Francisco, US to promote the project at international events. Athena-RC has presented ARIADNE at various meetings of the COSCH network (COST Action TD 1201, www.cosch.info).

5.2 National events

There have been a series of events organised at a national level (see the list of dissemination activities in Annex 2). Some highlights include:

- Il SITAR nella Rete della Ricerca Italiana Verso la conoscenza archeologica condivisa-Terzo Convegno, 23-24 May, 2013. Presentation of ARIADNE by PIN.
- LII National Archaeological Conference, Bulgaria, May 28-31, 2013. Presentation of ARIADNE by NIAM.
- Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past, UK, 6th July 2013. Poster by UoY-ADS and Discovery.
- CAA Konferensen, CAA-Sweden, 2-4 December 2013. Presentation by CNR.
- CAA-Germany annual meeting, 14-15 February 2014. Presentation by DAI.
- Launch of DARIAH-GR, 7 April 2014. Presentation by PIN.
- Risorse digitali e strumenti collaborativi per le Scienze dell'Antichità, 2nd October 2014, Venice, Italy (PIN),
- Austrian Days of Digital Humanities from ACDH at OEAW, 2nd December 2014, Vienna, Austria
- National Conference: Digital Archaeology, 21st April 2015, Amersfoort, Netherlands (KNAW_DANS)

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- Awareness raising exercise with politicians (TD & Senators) of Ireland, 13th May 2015, Dublin, Ireland (DISC)
- L'integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia, 1-2 October 2015, Lecce, Italy (PIN)
- Data Management Workshops, January 2016, in Vienna, Austria and Ljubljana, Slovenia
- ArcheoVirtual 2016 EXPO, Paestum, Italy, Presentation of the Virtual Museum of Calore Valley built with ARIADNE landscape services by CNR-ISTI.

In addition to events, there have been face-to-face meetings taking place at national level. For example, DISCOVERY has been having regular meetings with heritage stakeholders in Ireland who can potentially offer data to ARIDANE including the National Museum of Ireland, The Heritage Council, the National Monument Survey of Ireland, National Roads authority (NRA), Dublin City Council (DCC) and the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI). PIN attended a meeting with the Danish Humanities Research Infrastructures in Aarhus in May 2014.

5.3 ARIADNE 2014 conference, Rome

MiBACT-ICCU, with support from PIN, organized an international two-day conference on research infrastructures at the National Library in Rome in November 2014 as an official event under the Italian presidency of the EU. The focus was on Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures for Cultural Heritage and the programme included presentations from a series of research infrastructures including ARIADNE, CLARIN, CENDARI and OpenAIRE amongst others. The afternoon of the second day of the conference was devoted to ARIADNE and several presentations were made by Prof. Franco Nicolucci and work package leaders describing progress made during the first 18 months of the research infrastructure.

A booklet about ARIADNE was produced for launch at this event. This was presented to Zoran Stančič, Deputy Director-General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology (DG Connect) by Franco Nicolucci on behalf of the project.

There was a high level of press coverage in the Italian national newspapers (online and printed) as well as other countries, along with social media activity that boosted the profile of the project.

5.4 ARIADNE Final conference, Firenze

ARIADNE's final conference on the theme of "Unlocking the potential of digital archaeological data" was held in Florence on the 15th-16th December. The conference was held in a remarkably beautiful venue, the Sala di Luca Giordano at the Palazzo Medici-Riccardi in Florence. It provided a great showcase for the results being presented by speakers.

The conference opened with Franco Niccolucci setting the scene and describing how the ARIADNE research infrastructure has evolved from the initial ideas stage to the present day. Leonard de Wit, president of European Archaeological Consilium, followed by talking about the impact of digital technology on heritage management. The EAC's Amersfoort agenda is giving new impetus and opening archaeology practice to innovation.

Participants at the ARIADNE final conference

Felipe Criado-Boado, president of EAA, took open access and open subjectivity as his theme. Criado-Boado called for radical open access in archaeology with a move from open dissemination of knowledge to public service.

Luca Pezzati spoke next about E-RIHS and the development of a European research infrastructure for heritage science. Jennifer Edmond spoke about DARIADH-EU highlighting the flexibility of the ERIC structure to enable different kinds of contributions by members and the work that is going on to develop registries and offer training opportunities for members.

After the lunch break, Julian Richards (ADS) opened a session which gave a panoramic view of the services that have been developed in the ARIADNE project. Richards began the session by using the architecture of ARIADNE as an example of how archaeology can adapt the FAIR

ARIADNE D4.7 (Public)

principles of scientific data - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Re-usability. Achille Felicetti (PIN) presented the ARIADNE portal and registry explaining that the infrastructure now includes 1.85 million records. Carlo Meghini (CNR-ISTI) described the development of the ARIADNE catalogue data model, followed by Dimitris Gavriliis (Athena Research Centre) describing the ingestion tools and enrichment services that have been implemented in the ARIADNE registry.

Douglas Tudhope (University of South Wales) described the work that has been done by ARIADNE partners to map their vocabularies to the Getty's Art & Architecture thesaurus. Over 6,000 subject concepts from 27 vocabularies held by 12 partners have been mapped to AAT. Sebastian Cuy (DAI) then went on to demonstrate the ARIADNE portal showing how the subject mappings are supporting multi-lingual retrieval in the portal.

Panel of speakers at the ARIADNE conference

Achille Fellicetti spoke about the programme of "trans-national access", which has enable ARIADNE partners to host researchers as they worked on datasets and research projects. Roberto Scopigno (CNR-ISTI) demonstrated ARIADNE's visual media and landscape services. Hans Kammermans (Leiden University) spoke about ARIADNE's work on natural language processing and the interesting results that have been achieved. Then came Holly Wright (ADS) speaking about the new Guides to Good Practice and case studies that have been published by ARIADNE. The session was concluded by Hella Hollander (KNAW-DANS) who spoke about the importance of preservation of digital data in archaeology noting that for preservation data must be of good quality (FAIR) and must remain so.

The **second day** of the conference was chaired by Guntram Geser who began by speaking about the impact that ARIADNE has had on the researcher community. This was followed by a series of presentations from ARIADNE partners who spoke about the impact that the project has had on their organisations and in their countries.

Federico Nurra (INRAP) spoke of the considerable progress that INRAP has made in making their data available online as a result of ARIADNE. Edeltraud Aspöck (OEAW) spoke about the data management training that was delivered to staff and to researchers in Austria, and the access that has been opened to OEAW datasets from Neolithic Greece and Anatolia. Benjamin Štular (ZRC-SAZU) talked about the great connections made with people offering good advice on archaeological data management and how his organisation has been able to develop an overview regarding the situation with digital archaeological data in Romania. Attila Kreiter (HNM) spoke of the new online database made available by the Hungarian National Museum as a direct result of ARIADNE. Elisabeth Fentress (AIAC) spoke of the new services being developed by FASTI-Online inspired by ARIADNE.

The conference concluded with Franco Niccolucci speaking about the future of ARIADNE and the opportunities for collaboration, research, services and training. An ARIADNE association has been formed which it is hoped will enable the collaborations to continue.

Programme

Thursday 15th December

Welcome addresses by Authorities: Eugenio Giani, Presidente del Consiglio Regionale della Toscana; and Cristina Giachi, vice Sindaco di Firenze

The ARIADNE ecosystem: Towards a European Open Archaeological Cloud, Franco Niccolucci, PIN

Heritage management in the digital era, Leonard De Wit, EAC President

ARIADNE project and beyond: a view from EAA. From open access to open subjectivity? Felipe Criado-Boado, EAA President

Preparing E-RIHS -Towards the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science, Luca Pezzati, Coordinator E-RIHS & Iperion

Looking Forward with DARIAH EU, Jennifer Edmond, DARIAH Director

A panoramic view of the ARIADNE story led by Julian Richards, UoY-ADS

Improving Findability and Accessibility, contributions on ARIADNE's Portal and TNA activity

Improving Interoperability and Reusability, contributions on ARIADNE's services, tools, logical and theoretical models

Friday 16th December

The effect of ARIADNE: a success story

Why ARIADNE counts: ARIADNE impact, facts and figures, Guntram Geser, SRFG

Success stories from partners and the research community

The ARIADNE Roadmap: ways toward the future

A manifesto on forthcoming work, Franco Niccolucci, PIN and Julian Richards, UoY-ADS

6 Online access

6.1 Project website access statistics

Google Analytics was set up to record visits to the ARIADNE website as soon as the site was launched and all the statistics have been produced with this package.

Between 1st February 2013 and 31st December 2016, there were 53,849 sessions by 36,611 visitors with 184,074 page views.

The peaks in visitor traffic appear to relate to events where ARIADNE was presented, for example:

- The Research Infrastructures conference in Rome in November 2014, co-organized PIN and MIBACT was widely covered in the press
- The Computer Applications in Archaeology conferences in March 2014, 2015 and 2016
- The European Association of Archaeologists conference in September 2013 seems to have had more impact on use of the website than those of 2015 and 2016

Analysis of the visitor traffic across the four years of the project show a steady increase in the numbers of visitors, sessions and page views in each of the first three years. The slight decline in traffic during year 4 is a reflection of both the launch of the ARIADNE portal and the fact that the figures are for eleven months (February to December 2016) rather than twelve.

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Visitor Comparison	1 Feb '13 to 31 Jan '14	1 Feb '14 to 31 Jan '15	UP ^ DOWN V	1 Feb '15 to 31 Jan '16	UP ^ DOWN V	1 Feb '16 to 31 Dec '16*	UP ^ DOWN V
Sessions	9200	13422	^ 45.89%	16876	^ 25.73%	14351	V 14.96%
Users	6233	10072	^ 61.59%	12437	^ 23.48%	9806	V 21.15%
Pageviews	30982	43928	^ 41.79%	61324	^ 30.6%	47840	V 21.99%

* 11 month period

The web statistics show that the ARIADNE website has an international user base (see below). Europe is the main source of visitors 76% (down by 11%) with a further 6% from the United States of America. 2% from South Korea, 2% from Brazil, 1% from India and 1% from Russia.

Please note: While there are systems in place to prevent visits from site administrators being registered in the statistics (by IP and by website account), these systems are not 100% reliable and may result in inflated visit counts from the UK. It is also worth noting that Google Analytics does not record visits from users with JavaScript disabled. There are no accurate figures for the percentage of users with JavaScript disabled, but it is generally considered to be somewhere between 2% to 3%.

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Looking in more detail at the percentage of visits to the ARIADNE website by country, the top ten countries are: Italy (16.72%), UK (13.17%), Germany (6.76%), Greece (6.74%), United States (6.04%), France (5.92%), Austria (3.82%), Netherlands (3.63%), Spain (2.96%) and Ireland (2.21%).

Referrals

Referrals to the ARIADNE website lead to a total of 16,754 user sessions during the reporting period.

ARIADNE referrals are still dominated by Social Media – Facebook and Twitter account for 26% of these. It is pleasing to note that the ARIADNE portal now accounts for 4.01% of referrals to the project website. Other main sources of referrals were Archaeomatica.it (4.01%), Fasti Online (3.36%), KNAW DANS (2.73%), York.ac.uk (2.67%), DCU.gr (2.23%). Surveygizmo.com (2.21%) and ISTi-CNR (2.12%).

The following table shows the top 10 referrals (after the data has been cleaned to combine referrals from the same sources and the search bots have been removed).

Referral Source	Sessions	% Total
facebook.com	2,445	14.59%
t.co (Twitter)	1,807	10.79%
repubblica.it	797	4.76%
portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu	672	4.01%
archaeologydataservice.ac.uk	554	3.31%
fastionline.org	500	2.98%
york.ac.uk	448	2.67%
dcu.gr	373	2.23%
surveygizmo.com	370	2.21%
vcg.isti.cnr.it	355	2.12%
Other	8433	50.33%
Total	16,754	100.00%

Top content

The most frequently viewed pages on the ARIADNE site were: Home (16.58%), 2015 TNA call (5.1%), About (5.01%), Resources (4.55%), Events (3.45%), Services (3.43) and Community (2.64).

Top 10 Content	Pageviews	% Total
Home	30,519	16.58%
Services/2015-TNA-call	9,382	5.10%
About	9,221	5.01%
Resources	8,375	4.55%
Events	6,356	3.45%
Services	6,314	3.43%
Community	4,860	2.64%
News	4,608	2.50%
Portal	2,017	1.10%
Online -Services	1,556	0.85%
Other	100,873	54.80%
Total	184,074	100.00%

6.2 Access to data services

During 2014, ARIADNE launched Trans National Access (TNA) to online services offered by three partners:

- Archaeology Data Service: ARCHSEARCH.
- AIAC (the International Association for Classical Archaeology): FASTI Online
- Deutsches Archäologisches Institut: ARACHNE and ZENON.

In 2015 and 2016 the ARIADNE online services became available:

- Visual Media Service: <http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>
- Landscape Services: <http://landscape.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>
- ARIADNE portal: <http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

In addition the ARIADNE portal provides a register of services offered by ARIADNE partners (<http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/services>) including:

- KNAW-DANS Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology
- IDAI.vocab and IDAI.gazetter – the DAI thesaurus of Archaeological concepts and gazetteer of placenames
- Heritage Data: Vocabulary matching tool
- MeshLab

Various dissemination activities have been carried out to promote these online services throughout the project period including news items via the project newsletter, twitter and other social media, tweets about searches of the day, etc.

Sections were created on the project website for the Portal and online services (<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Portal>).

Google Analytics was set up to record visits to the ARIADNE portal from the outset. Access to ARIADNE online services is reported in detail in D5.3, an overview is included in this deliverable for monitoring purposes.

Between 1st December 2015 and 5th January 2017, there were 15,400 sessions by 10,819 visitors. There were 68,982 page views with an average of 4.48 pages viewed per sessions, which had an average duration of 3.31 minutes. 70% of sessions were new.

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The graph shows that there was an increase in user activity on the ARIADNE portal from July 2016 onwards. This coincides with the start of a campaign in which searches of the week were tweeted to ARIADNE followers.

The site demographics suggest that there is a worldwide audience for the ARIADNE portal. During this period, the UK has provided the main source of visitors (50%), followed by France (7.3%), Italy (5.86%), the United States (4.13%), Greece (4.08%), Ireland (3.34%), Germany (3.1%), the Netherlands (2.5%), Russia (2.49%) and Sweden (1.82%).

7 Monitoring indicators

The dissemination programme has been monitored and evaluated to review:

- What messages (communication of benefits) are going out and who is seeing them;
- Whether those messages are being understood and remembered, and;
- Whether the messages are influencing opinions, attitudes and behaviours.

This information has helped in planning subsequent phases of the dissemination strategy, in developing activities and in updating the dissemination plan.

Success indicators

Description		Month 48 target	Month 48 actual
Stakeholder involvement	No. of institutions	100 ✓	More than 135 different institutions have been involved in ARIADNE. This number includes associate partners, institutions/projects that have exchanged cooperation agreements, institutions that have sent researchers to participate in TNA and ARIADNE training workshops, institutions that participated in bilateral meetings with ARIADNE and which invited presentations by ARIADNE partners, and those which participated in ARIADNE user surveys. The number does not include all the institutions represented by researchers who have taken part in conference sessions and workshops.
User involvement	No of participants	250 ✓	At least 10,500 users have participated in ARIADNE activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C. 3000 participants in events organized by ARIADNE • c. 9,500 participants attending presentations given by ARIADNE partners in conferences and workshops organized by others • c. 500 participants in ARIADNE TNA and training workshops • 692 researchers and data managers participated in the user-needs surveys. The figure of 10,500 users reached takes into account an estimate that 25% of people will

			have participated in more than one ARIADNE.
Project website	Visitors	12000 ✓	36,611 visitors to the website in 53,849 sessions between 1 st February 2013 and 5 th January 2017.
Research infrastructure online services	Anonymous users	800 ✓	10,819 visitors to the ARIADNE portal in 15,400 session between 1 st January 2016 and 5 th January 2017.
Research infrastructure online services	Registered users	600	Following discussion ARIADNE services were developed without requiring users to register.
Social networks	No of members	1500 ✓	754 Followers on Twitter. The impact of re-tweeting of ARIADNE news by partners and other followers dramatically extends the reach to around 160,000 unique users. 39 members on LinkedIn 21 members on Facebook 11 followers on SlideShare 348 members on the project website.
Presentations at international events	No. of participants*	3000 ✓	ARIADNE partners participated in c 150 international conferences, workshops and meetings attended by c. 4,500 users. The number of participants was reported by partners for c 58% of events; the total number of participants is based on an average of 30 users attending each event.
Good practice guides accessed	No. unique visitors	1500 ✓	1275 unique page views to Dendrochronology Guide to Good Practice 409 unique page views to 3D models Guide to Good Practice 348 unique page views to ARIADNE case study on Big data 50 unique page views to ARIADNE case study on Dendrochronology of Early Medieval Emporium Dorestad
Newsletters	Readers	300 ✓	410 subscribers who receive the newsletter directly.

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The following statistics are available for the project website and products such as the Guides to Good Practice:

- Page views
- Unique visitors
- Return visitors
- Visits
- Amount of time spent on the site/bounce rate
- Visitor's country
- Referral data (search terms)

Achievement of dissemination plan objectives:

Objective	Description & planned activity	Activity
Objective 1	<p>Establishing the project website and portal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing and building the project website and social media accounts • Developing the project website adding new content • Preparing for the launch of the integrated portal and registries 	<p>The website was established in the first month of the project and has been developed and improved throughout. News, project reports, presentations and other content have been added to the site regularly. During 2015-16 the major activities have been the launch of the ARIADNE services and portal, which have greatly increased overall visitor traffic to the sites.</p>
Objective 2	<p>Extending the stakeholder database:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building the contact database • Developing the project's presence on the social networks. • Cooperating with existing communities such as EAA, CAA and research infrastructures 	<p>The project has been continued to be active in disseminating news, participating in events and establishing collaborations with research infrastructures, institutions, EAA, CAA and others.</p> <p>A bibliography for the project has been established on Zotero. A substantial number of project deliverables and presentations have been uploaded to Slideshare where they have attracted a sizable number of views.</p> <p>Partners have been active in sharing news about the project via their websites, newsletters, and social</p>

		media account.
Objective 3	<p>Informing the stakeholder community about news, events, project activities and transnational access to the infrastructure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posting news and information regularly via the website and social networks. • Producing the project newsletter • Disseminating project presentations and documents via SlideShare. • Press notices 	<p>The project has disseminated project news, calls and other information regularly via the website and the social networks. Social media is driving traffic to specific pages on the website, for example the calls for TNA access.</p> <p>9 issues of the project newsletter have been produced.</p> <p>Twitter has been used regularly to disseminate project news, calls and other information. The impact of retweeting of ARIADNE news by partners and other followers dramatically extends the reach of the stakeholder database to around 160,000. Social media is driving traffic to specific pages on the website, for example the calls for TNA access.</p> <p>91 presentations and 27 documents have been uploaded to SlideShare during the period.</p> <p>3 press notices were prepared to announce the project launch, the Research Infrastructures conference in Rome and the final project event.</p>
Objective 4	<p>Informing the research community about transnational access and training opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing the transnational access selection panel. • Preparing the calls to researchers to put forwards proposals for 	<p>External experts were invited to participate in the TNA user selection panel again.</p> <p>The 2014, 2015 and 2016 calls for TNA access were prepared and published on the project website. The calls have been widely disseminated to researchers.</p> <p>Materials and user feedback from</p>

	<p>access.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of dissemination channels to advertise training opportunities to researchers. 	<p>the TNA have also been disseminated.</p>
Objective 5	<p>Developing the set of dissemination materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project brochure • Templates for case studies and fact sheets • Project poster 	<p>The set of project dissemination materials has been maintained and updated. Flyers have been produced for specific events. Two project booklets have been printed for dissemination at project events, digital copies have been published online. The first project booklet has received more than 6000 views on SlideShare.</p>
Objective 6	<p>Presenting the project at relevant international and national events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project presentations • ARIADNE Workshops and conference sessions • Final ARIADNE conference 	<p>The project was presented at more than 250 international and national events during the project, reaching more than 12,500 attendees. In addition, around 425 researchers have participated in short training courses and workshops organized by ARIADNE.</p>

8 Conclusion

This deliverable presents ARIADNE's dissemination activities during the whole project period (months one to forty eight).

Raising awareness about the project and about the management, access and preservation of digital archaeological datasets in national and international contexts have been the main aim of the dissemination strategy. To deliver this strategy the project has worked to build the stakeholder community communicating the project's results through events, publications, the media, social networks and by networking activities. It has developed a set of dissemination materials including a web environment, printed and electronic matter for use by the partners.

The project has set out to involve the community in its activities and has reached out to stakeholders in a range of ways. Partners have organized 65 separate events (including conference sessions and workshops) and have participated in around 150 other events (delivering conference papers, posters etc.) that were attended by approximately 12,500 individuals. More than 500 researchers have taken part in ARIADNE Trans National Access visits, training events and short training courses. In addition to these events more than 700 researchers and managers participated in user surveys run by ARIADNE. Partners have had 85 articles relating to the project published in journals, conference proceedings, books and other publications.

The impact of ARIADNE's dissemination and awareness raising activities has been significant in terms of both raising awareness of ARIADNE services, the value of archaeological datasets and the importance of good practices, open access to data and "next generation skills".

ARIADNE's final conference in Florence in December 2016 marked the end of the project phase. Thanks to the enthusiasm and passion of ARIADNE partners it also marked a new beginning with the launch of the ARIADNE association.

9 References

Annex I – “Description of Work”-DoW

ARIADNE website: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

ARIADNE, 2013, D4.1 ARIADNE website: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

ARIADNE, 2013, D4.2 ARIADNE initial dissemination plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

ARIADNE, 2014, D4.3 First period dissemination report and second period dissemination plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D4.3-First-period-dissemination-report-and-second-period-dissemination-plan>

ARIADNE, 2014, D4.4 Initial report on good practices: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D4.4-Initial-Report-on-Good-Practices>

ARIADNE, 2014, D2.1 First report on users’ needs: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D2.1-First-report-on-users-needs>

ARIADNE, 2015, D2.2 Second report on users' needs: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/content/view/full/1188>

ARIADNE, 2015, D2.3 Preliminary Innovation Agenda and Action Plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D2.3-Preliminary-Innovation-Agenda-and-Action-Plan>

ARIADNE, 2015, D5.2 Initial report on the assessment of online access: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D5.2-Report-on-the-Initial-Assessment-of-Online-Access>

ARIADNE, 2016, D4.6 Final report on good practices: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D4.6-Final-Report-on-Good-Practices>

ARIADNE, 2016, D4.5, Second period dissemination report and third period dissemination plan: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources/D4.5-Second-period-dissemination-report-and-third-period-dissemination-plan>

ARIADNE, 2017, D5.1 Report on transnational access activities and training activities: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

ARIADNE, 2017, D5.3 Final report on the assessment of online access: <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

10 Annex 1: List of dissemination activities

Date	Place and Country	Event + URL of website	Note	Partner
February 2013				
18	Rome	Workshop with National heads of the Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani, to create a unified digital dataset of sculpture. DAI, Rome.		DAI AIAC
March 2013				
22	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Arheologija v letu 2013 - dediščina za javnost (Archaeology in 2013 - heritage for the public) http://arheoportalsi/predavanja/arheologija-v-letu-2012--dediscina-za-javnost	Presentation of ARIADNE project	ZRC SAZU
25-28	Perth, Australia	CAA 2013, www.caa2013.org	Session "Archaeological Information Modelling" Workshop "Hands-On Archaeological Conceptual Modelling" Paper "Expressing Temporal and Subjective Information about Archaeological Entities"	CSIC
25-28	Perth, Australia	CAA 2013 www.caa2013.org	ARIADNE project poster	Discovery, UoY-ADS
April 2013				
08-10	Porto, Portugal	ECLAP 2013, 2nd International Conference on Information Technologies for Performing Arts, Media Access and Entertainment http://www.eclap.eu/drupal/?q=node/113965	Presented paper- ARIADNE: "Validating the Digital Documentation of Cultural Objects"	PIN
12	Groningen, The Netherlands	SOJA conference (Symposium Onderzoek Jonge Archeologen) http://archeologieonline.nl/nieuws/symposium-onderzoek-jonge-archeologen-2013	Flyer handed out to 150 starting/young archaeologists	KNAW-DANS

22-24	Siena, Italy	Mind the Gap - international seminar http://thelrc.wordpress.com/2013/02/22/mind-the-gap-an-international-seminar-on-emptiness-visibility-ambiguity-and-absence-in-archaeology/	ARIADNE - materials	DAI
May 2013				
6	Xi'an, China	Sustainable Archaeology	Presentation: 'Digital Data in archaeology: long term preservation and access'	UoY-ADS
13-17	Merida	CIAC congress http://aiac2013merida-mnar.icac.net/	ARIADNE presentation	AIAC
23-24	Rome, Italy	Il SITAR nella Rete della Ricerca Italiana Verso la conoscenza archeologica condivisa- Terzo Convegno http://www.garr.it/a/eventi/eventi-comunita/details/94-convegno-sitar-2013 .	Presentation of ARIADNE project c.50 participants	PIN
27-30	Nicosia, Cyprus	Virtual Heritage School on Digital Cultural Heritage, Nicosia	Presentation of ARIADNE project C. 20 young archaeologists	PIN, CYI-STARC
28	Bristol, UK	UK & Irish Isotopes Group Workshop	ARIADNE - Scientific data integration/ Coordination with national initiatives	DISCOVERY
29-30	Paris, France	RCIS 2013	Paper "Modelling Temporality and Subjectivity in ConML"	CSIC
29-30 June	Vienna, Austria	10th International Conference on Archaeological Prospection, Austrian Academy of Sciences, http://ap2013.univie.ac.at/	ARIADNE poster & materials	OEAW
31	Hissar, Bulgaria	LII National Archaeological Conference, May 28-31, 2013 http://naim.bg/bg/content/news/600/EAA_conference_857/357/	ARIADNE announced as a part of the progress of AIS AKB in 2013 (by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov)	NIAM-BAS

June 2013				
3-7	Stockholm, Sweden	CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting	Proposal: integration of a part of CRMgeo (which is part of the ARIADNE Global Model) to the CIDOC-CRM core classes.	FORTH
13-15	Pisa	MAPPA final conference: Opening the Past http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/?page_id=136&lang=en Archaeology of the Future, in MapPapers 1-III, 2013, pp. 42-43 MapPapers 1-III	Keynote speech on Open Archaeology (ADS). Paper (KNAW-DANS): Past the Opening: building towards the present, on-going dissemination of Dutch archaeological data as part of the DANS archive. c. 75 archaeologists	UoY-ADS and KNAW-DANS
July 2013				
5	Marburg	Colloquium: Hessian Department of Archaeology	ARIADNE - materials	DAI
6	York, UK	Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past http://www.york.ac.uk/digital-heritage/events/cdh-2013/	ARIADNE poster	UoY-ADS Discovery
22-26	Indianapolis, Indiana, USA	JCDL 2013 www.jcdl2013.org	Disseminate news about ARIADNE	Athena RC
September 2013				
2-5	Lisbon, Portugal	iPRES 2013 http://ipres2013.ist.utl.pt/	Paper: Preservation Aspects of a Curation-Oriented Thematic Aggregator	Athena RC
4	Pilsen, Czech Republic	Data Management Planning and Online Resources for Archaeology Workshop http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/ARIADNE-Workshop-EAA-2013	ARIADNE training workshop on data management planning and transnational access c. 25 researchers	UoY-ADS, SRFG, SND, KNAW-DANS, DAI, AIAC

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4-7	Pilsen, Czech Republic	EAA conference session, "New digital developments in heritage Management and research " http://proposal.eaa2013.cz/programe/session-abstract.php?id=9	Conference session included introductions to ARIADNE c. 70 archaeologists	UoY-ADS and PIN
4-7	Pilsen	EAA 2013, in the Session "Towards a real representation and interpretation of spatio-temporal data in Archaeological Record"	Paper "An ontological spatio-temporal refinement for the CIDOC CRM and GIS standards"	FORTH
6	Copenhagen	DARIAH VCC meeting	ARIADNE update presentation	PIN
17	Weimar, Germany	3D PITOTI Workshop www.pitoti.org	ARIADNE – distribution of materials	DAI
19-21	Padova, Italy	12th European Meeting on Ancient Ceramics (EMAC2013)	Disseminate news about ARIADNE to the archaeometry community	CSIC
20-26	Pontignano, Siena, Italy	International Summer School "Drones applied to Cultural Heritage and Archaeology" http://www.archeomatica.it/images/images/UAVsummerchool2013.pdf	Introduction of ARIADNE to participants	CNR ITABC
20	Cottbus, Germany	KickOff Event of DFG project "OpenInfRA"	ARIADNE presentation to possible partners	DAI
24-25	Amersfoort, Netherlands	ArcLand plenary meeting 2013 https://www.surveymonkey.com/s.aspx?sm=2bpsEmpZ_2bqRFSKx_2fat8Fnig_3d_3d	Participation by ARIADNE partners; networking and collaboration opportunity	ARUP CAS, Discovery
25	Zeist, The Netherlands	SIKB conference, http://www.sikb.nl/11715 http://www.sikb.nl/365	Lecture about the protocol for uniform data exchange for Dutch archaeologists	KNAW-DANS
26-28	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	AARG Conference 2013 http://www.decars.nl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=124&Itemid=76&lang=en	Paper "Integrating ALS, aerial prospection and ground-based survey into the study of visible	ARUP CAS

			and hidden components of post-medieval military open landscapes” “From find to structure”	
26	Valetta, Malta	CRMEX workshop at TPD2013 Malta http://tpdl2013.upatras.gr/ http://tpdl2013.upatras.gr/ws-crmex.php	Paper: Quality management of 3D cultural heritage replicas with CIDOC-CRM Paper: European standards for the documentation of historic buildings and their relationship with CIDOC-CRM Paper: Mapping ICCD Archaeological Data to CIDOC-CRM: the RA Schema	PIN FORTH
October 2013				
4-5	Gothenburg, Sweden	DASISH Gothenburg workshop, 4-5 October 2013: http://dasish.eu/events/2013/wsssh	ARIADNE presentation	PIN
21	Kilkenny, Ireland	Heritage Council Workshop - Addressing digital heritage data in Ireland	ARIADNE - Coordination with national initiatives	Discovery
22	Heraklion, Greece	CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting	Presented CRMarchaeo (part of the ARIADNE Global Model) to the CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting c. 20 participants	FORTH PIN
28-2	Marseilles, France	Digital Heritage 2013, Int. Conf.	Paper: "A computer-assisted constraint-based system for assembling fragmented objects" (CNR) Interviews (WP 2.1) with Conference attendees, networking. Dissemination of Fliers (DAI)	CNR DAI

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29	Rome	Presentation of ARIADNE to possible associated partners	Meeting PIN-ICCU-ICCD	PIN
November 2013				
13	Vienna	CHNT2013 conference session, "Infrastructures and services for sharing of archaeological documentation" http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/CHNT-Workshop-2013	Session organised and chaired by SRFG with support from OEAW and presentations by several partners. c. 40 researchers	SRFG, OEAW KNAW-DANS CSIC, FORTH Athena RC CNR, SND Discovery
19-22	Thessaloniki, Greece	MTSR 2013 http://mtsr2013.teithe.gr/	Special Track on Metadata & Semantics for Cultural Collections & Applications	Athena RC UoG
19	Prato	Meeting with representatives from Getty Institute, Farallon and World Monument Fund.	Presentation of ARIADNE.	PIN
20	Graz, Austria	DARIAH Workshop DH2014 http://informationsmodellierung.uni-graz.at/de/aktuelles/dariah-workshop-dh-2014/	Short presentation of ARIADNE	OEAW
21-22	Berlin, Germany	"Facing the future" workshop, Berlin 21-22 November 2013: http://facingthefuture.gwi-berlin.de/	Presentation: "The ARIADNE approach to digital cultural heritage" c. 80-90 digital humanities researchers	PIN
20-22	Nečtiny, Czech Republic	Conference "Archaeology and the Public 7" http://www.emuzeum.cz/konference-v-cr-a-sr/archeologie-pro-budoucnost-archeologie-a-verejnost-7-2013.html	Paper "Map of aerial archaeological sites"	ARUP CAS
29	Sofia, Bulgaria	Second PhD student conference "Research of cultural-historical heritage: provocations and prospects" http://naim.bg/en/content/news/600/857/394/	A presentation about AIS AKB and its development in the recent years; ARIADNE project mention	NIAM-BAS
29	Rome	Seminar on Linked Open Data	Presentation of ARIADNE work on Metadata	PIN

December 2013				
2 - 4	Lund, Sweden	CAA Konferensen, CAA-Sweden https://sites.google.com/site/caasweden/konferens-2013	Invited keynote speech about ARIADNE c. 60 Participants	CNR
4	London	Meeting at British Museum	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN CYI-STARC
11	Berlin, Germany	Pelagios Gazetteer Meeting http://pelagios-project.blogspot.de/2014/01/the-day-of-pelagios-berlin-111213.html	Presentation of ARIADNE focusing on extending CIDOC-CRM	DAI, FORTH
13	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Seminar organised by Faculty of Archaeology of the University of Ljubljana about trends, developments and knowledge in archaeological archiving.	Lectures: "EASY and the archaeological data management workflow at DANS" and "Preserving the archaeological record of the Netherlands: The establishment of the e-Depot for Dutch Archaeology on standards and regulations"	KNAW-DANS`
19- 21	Jodhpur, India	NCVPRIPG 2013 - National Conference on Computer Vision, Pattern Recognition, Image Processing and Graphics http://www.iitj.ac.in/ncvprig/	Invited keynote speech: "High-fidelity 3D models for Cultural Heritage"	CNR
January 2014				
2-4	Chicago, Illinois, USA	Annual Meetings, Archaeological Institute of America	Presentation of ARIADNE in context of Fasti Online award. Meetings with Open Context, tDAR, North Carolina Ancient World Mapping Center dARMC	AIAC
20- 22	Casablanca, Morocco	Africa-EU Workshop on the Fight Against Illegal Trafficking of Cultural Goods.	ARIADNE presentation	DAI
20- 22	Berlin, Germany	DAI IT Days	ARIADNE presentation	DAI

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21	Catania, Italy	DCH-RP plenary meeting http://www.dch-rp.eu/	Presentation of ARIADNE; opportunities for collaboration between the two projects c. 40 participants	PIN
February 2014				
6	Pisa, Italy	Italian National info day on R1 H2020-APRE	Presentation of ARIADNE in the framework of SSH Ris, Collaboration with research infrastructure projects c.250 participants	PIN
12	Timioara, Romania	Public lectures on the on-going urban archaeology in the center of Timisoara	Introducing citizens the results of the on-going excavations in the center of the city within a European perspective	Arheovest
13	Frankfurt, Germany	Event of Bundesamt für Kartografie/ Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy	ARIADNE introduction, distribution of flyers	DAI
14-15	Tübingen, Germany	CAA-Germany annual meeting http://ag-caa.de	Multiple topics of interest, networking	DAI
18	Rome, Italy	Workshop with National heads of the Corpus Signorum Imperii Romani, to create a unified digital dataset of sculpture. DAI, Rome.	Networking	AIAC
March 2014				
17-18	Seville, Spain	Workshop at Instituto Andaluz del Patrimonio Historico	Presentation of ARIADNE to Director and senior managers of the institute Cooperation agreement 10 participants	PIN
20-21	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	15 th EAC Heritage Management Symposium, European Archaeological Council http://www.european-archaeological-council.org/16-0-Symposia.html	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 150 Archaeologists and CH managers	PIN

23	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Arheologija v letu 2013 - dediščina za javnost (Archaeology in 2013 - heritage for the public) http://arheoportalsi/predavanja/arheologija-v-letu-2012--dediscina-za-javnost	Presentation of ARIADNE	ZRC-SAZU
24-25	Sofia, Bulgaria	International conference 5th Danube Limes Brand, Project Meeting http://danubelimesbrand.org/news-events/project-meeting/	ARIADNE presentation (Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov and Nadezhda Kecheva)	NIAM-BAS
26	Prato, Italy	Meeting with delegation of Chinese Universities	Presentation of ARIADNE 25 professors from Chinese and Italian Universities and local government officers	PIN
April 2014				
2	Athens, Greece	ICRI Conference, 2 nd International Conference on Research Infrastructures. http://www.icri2014.eu/	Networking and informal presentation of ARIADNE c. 400 participants	PIN
2-4	The Hague, Netherlands	CIDOC-CRM SIG meeting	CRMsciv1.2 was discussed (issue 229)	FORTH
7-9	Timisoara, Romania	The "other" school	Archaeological activities with school children	Arheovest
7	Athens, Greece	Launch of DARIAH-GR http://www.dias-net.gr/kickoff/?page_id=319	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 100 Greek researchers	PIN
9	Glasgow, UK	IfA 2014 http://www.archaeologists.net/conference/2014info	Paper: Navigating Collaborative European Projects in Archaeology c. 50 archaeologists	UoY-ADS
9	Laval, France	Laval Virtual 2014 (Exhibition and conference), http://www.laval-virtual.org/en/	Invited talk on "Virtual clones for Cultural Heritage applications" at the Digital heritage Symposium	CNR-ISTI

9	Boston, Mass, USA	Meeting with DARMC (Digital Atlas of Roman and Medieval Civilisations) http://darmc.harvard.edu/icb/icb.do	Presentation of ARIADNE	AIAC
10-11	Timisoara, Romania	Bridging the Danube international conference organized by the American Research Center in Sofia	Representatives: Largest Romanian academic and research institutions, Poland, Serbia	Arheovest
12	Timisoara, Romania	Exhibition - The Dacians in the Banat plains	Exhibition on the archaeological activities of Arheovest	Arheovest
14	Leiden, Netherlands	Odyssee symposium at the Dutch National Museum of Antiquities (RMO): Presenting new results of research on old excavation data which was not analysed before.	Introduced ARIADNE to Dutch Archaeological project leaders during the interactive panel discussion	KNAW-DANS
16	Amersfoort Netherlands	RCC Symposium, the Netherlands Cultural Heritage Agency	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 60 Officers from RCE and researchers from Dutch Universities	PIN
18	Utrecht, Netherlands	CLARIN ESFRI	Presentation of ARIADNE c. 5 CLARIN Directors	PIN
22	Paris, France	CAA 2014, "Online resources for Archaeology Research" http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/	ARIADNE Workshop	UoY-ADS, AIAC, DAI, KNAW-DANS, PIN
22-25	Paris, France	CAA 2014, partners organised a number of workshops and sessions held during the conference. http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/	Workshop "Hands-On Archaeological Conceptual Modelling 2" (CSIC) Session "Modelling the Archaeological Process", highly related to ARIADNE (CSIC) Session "GIS, a new trowel for archaeologists? The challenges of using GIS in preventive	CSIC, Discovery INRAP, PIN, CYI-STARC

			archaeology” (Discovery INRAP) Round table: “Virtual archaeology, the first 25 years” (PIN, CYI-STARC)	
22-25	Paris, France	CAA 2014, several partners presented individual papers or posters during the conference. http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/	Paper “The Development of Data Sharing and Open Data in Archaeology” (ADS) Paper “Integration of Archaeological Datasets Through the Gradual Refinement of Models” (CSIC) Paper: “Dykes of standards supporting polders of data / The practices used in the Netherlands for making archaeological data available and accessible” (KNAW-DANS) Poster - Perception and Adoption of Landscape: Recent Model and Its Use in Study of Prehistoric Settlement Strategies (ARUP CAS)	UoY-ADS CSIC KNAW-DANS ARUP CAS
23	Timisoara, Romania	Association of archaeology and ancient history	Weekly seminars on archaeology for students and young scholars	Arheovest
24	Austin, Texas, USA	SAA 2014 http://www.saa.org/AbouttheSociety/AnnualMeeting/2014Program/tabid/1508/Default.aspx	Paper: A European perspective on representing and interpreting spatial data from archaeological fieldwork as Linked Open Data	UoY-ADS UoG FORTH
28	Rome, Italy	Presentation of IPERION CH CHARISMA partnership and other European institutions	Presentation of ARIADNE, discussion about collaboration opportunities c. 60 Researchers in conservation and preservation	PIN

May 2014				
6	Aarhus, Denmark	Meeting with Danish Humanities Research Infrastructures	Presentation of ARIADNE and discussion of collaboration opportunities c. 30 Researchers	PIN
8-10	Budapest, Hungary	"New Approaches to the Temple of Zeus at Olimpia: Architecture, sculpture, history and new technologies" http://www.archaeological.org/events/14369	Workshop on archaeological research and use of 3D graphics for study and dissemination	CNR-ISTI
25-27	Smolenice, Slovakia	18th Central European Seminar on Computer Graphics organized by TUWien	Invited talk on the ARIADNE project	CNR
26-30	Prato, Italy	"Mapping existing datasets to CIDOC-CRM", ARIADNE TNA summer school	ARIADNE TNA summer school 5 researchers	PIN, FORTH
28-30	Marrakech, Morocco	RCIS 2014	Paper "An ISO/IEC 24744-Derived Modelling Language for Discourse Analysis"	CSIC
30-31	Sandanski, Bulgaria	LIII National Archaeological Conference, May 28-31, 2013	ARIADNE development will be presented as a part of the progress of AIS AKB in 2014 (by Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgi Nekhrizov)	NIAM-BAS
June 2014				
2-4	Luxembourg	13 th meeting of the Member states expert group on digitisation	Networking	MIBACT-ICCU
4	Rome, Italy	Meeting with EAGLE project http://www.eagle-network.eu/	Presentation of ARIADNE, collaboration opportunity 10 EAGLE steering committee members	PIN CYI-STARC
10	Rome, Italy	Meeting with CENIEH http://www.cenieh.es/en	Presentation of ARIADNE, collaboration opportunity 5 representatives	PIN

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10-12	Grenoble, France	Colloque Patrimoine et Humanités numériques http://www.msh-alpes.fr/fr/colloque-patrimoine-humanites-numeriques	Networking	MIBACT-ICCU
11-12	Deva, Romania	Deva regional county museum, scientific event	ARIADNE presentation	Arheovest
11-13	Glasgow, UK	European Network for Archaeology and Integrated Landscape Research: workshop http://www.gla.ac.uk/schools/humanities/research/archaeologyresearch/groups/heritagephilosophypractice/	Introduction of ARIADNE, distribution of flyers	DAI
20	Rome, Italy	Tecnologie digitali per i beni culturali http://www.ambafrence.it.org/Conferenza-Tecnologie-digitali-per	Presentation of ARIADNE	CNR
23-24	Athens, Greece	Europeana Strategy meeting on Research & Tourism http://www.gr2014.eu/events/parallel-events/europeana-v3-event-%E2%80%9Ceuropa-research-and-tourism%E2%80%9D	Networking	MiBACT-ICCU
30	Bari, Italy	Rights management in the implementation of the Digital Library http://www.regione.puglia.it/index.php?page=calendario&opz=display&id=2036	Presentation: ICCU experiences in International projects	MiBACT-ICCU
30-3	Apsley, England	ARCHES Community workshop	Presentation of ARIADNE 30 culture professionals and software developers	PIN
July 2014				
8	Lausanne, Switzerland	Digital Humanities, DH2014, GeoHumanities SIG meeting. dh2014.org	Presentation: Effective design and use of a Spatiotemporal Gazetteer	DAI

10	London, UK	EVA London 2014, "Learning Opportunities for Sharing Data in the ARIADNE Project" http://www.eva-london.org/past-eva-londons/past-eva-londons/2014	ARIADNE training workshop Presentation of ARIADNE TNA summer schools	PIN
11	Brighton, UK	A Future for our Past - Research in Digital Technologies for Arts, Heritage and Archaeology	Invited talk and presentation on ARIADNE	PIN
September 2014				
6	Dresden, Germany	CIDOC2014 Access and Understanding– Networking in the Digital Era http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/home/program-information/workshops-en	Tutorial on CRMsci and CRMarchaeo for 10 archaeologists	FORTH
10-13	Istanbul, Turkey	EAA 2014 http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/home/program-information/workshops-en	Workshop: Opportunities Within The Ariadne Network Session: "Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology", 16 presentations, incl. by English Heritage, SRFG and UoY. c. 42 EAA members	(Workshop) PIN, CNR, ATHENA CETI (Session) SRFG and UoY (co-chairs)
12	London, UK	Semantics & Cultural Heritage meet-up at The British Museum http://www.slideshare.net/MariaTheodoridou/london-meetup2014-mappingchi2cidoccrm	Presentation of Mapping the dFMRÖ coin database to CIDOC-CRM TO C. 20 archaeologists, IT researchers	FORTH, OEAW
22	Rome, Italy	Final Conference DCH-RP project	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN
29 – 2 Oct	Heraklion, Greece	CIDOC-CRM Special Interest Group Meeting http://cidoc-crm.org/special_interest_meetings.html	Presentation of CRMarchaeo: the Excavation Model, An Extension of CIDOC-CRM to support archaeological excavations to 15 SIG members	FORTH

October 2014				
2	Venice, Italy	Risorse digitali e strumenti collaborativi per le Scienze dell'Antichità	Distributed flyers	PIN
6-9	Darmstadt Germany	Eurographics Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage: GCH 2014 http://diglib.eg.org/GCH2014/	Presentation of scientific papers and a State of the Art Report to c. 60 CH & IT participants	CNR
27-31	Amantea, Italy	ODBASE 2014, The conference on Ontologies, DataBases, and Applications of Semantics for Large Scale Information Systems	Presentation of the paper: Designing and implementing data registries: A case study for archaeology	CNR ISTI, Athena
November 2014				
10	Prato, Italy	Joint workshop between PIN, and the ARCHES developer team (Getty Conservation Institute/Word Monuments Funds and the Farallon Geographics team)	Presentation of ARIADNE activities and discussion about collaboration	PIN
13-14	Rome, Italy	ARIADNE symposium at International conference on Research Infrastructure and e-Infrastructures for Digital Cultural Heritage.	Participation at workshop – over 200 attendees.	PIN, KNAW-DANS, ARUP_CAS, UoY-ADS
20	Hague, Netherlands	Reuvenstdagen	Poster on national conference for Dutch archaeologists – c. 600	KNAW-DANS
28	Rovereto, Italy	Lo scavo archeometrico (the archaeometric excavation) http://www.agiati.it/ara_news.jsp?ID_NEWS=1129&areaNews=192&GTemplate=ara_home.jsp,	Presentation of ARIADNE and the services CNR is developing to 50 archaeology professionals	CNR

December 2014				
2	Vienna, Austria	Austrian Days of Digital Humanities from ACDH at OEAW http://acdh.ac.at/de/savethedata-workshop	Workshop on repositories: paper about EDNA/DANS at workshop "Save the data" to c. attendees	OEAW, KNAW-DANS
January 2015				
18	Budapest, Hungary	Meeting at the Hungarian National Museum	ARIADNE presented to Gyula Forster National Centre for Cultural Heritage Management	MNM-NOK
February 2015				
10-12	Oxford, UK	CIDOC CRM SIG	Presentation of the ontological models CRMarchaeo and CRMba	PIN
March 2015				
4	Rome, Italy	Workshop "Accesso aperto al patrimonio culturale digitale e linked open data: strategie, progetti e nuove opportunità", Roma http://www.otebac.it/index.php?it/22/archivio-eventi/260/roma-workshop-accesso-aperto-al-patrimonio-culturale-digitale-e-linked-open-data-strategie-progetti-e-nuove-opportunita	Presentation of ARIADNE	PIN
6-8	Pompeii, Italy	Stvdivm Ad Observabilia Aperienda (STVDIVM) http://www.openpompei.it/2015/02/04/open-archaeological-data-in-pompeii/	Julian Richards, keynote on Open Data in European Archaeology	ADS
11-12	Nicosia CY	EAGLE Conference http://www.eagle-network.eu/about/events/fifth-eagle-international-event-2015/	Presentation of ARIADNE activities: Mapping Tools and Interoperability	PIN
18-21	Lisbon, Portugal	EAC Archaeological Archiving Working Group http://european-archaeological-	EAC annual meeting	ADS

		council.org/activities-and-events/annual-meetings/eac-annual-meeting-18-21-march-2015-lisbon-portugal		
30-3	Siena, Italy	CAA 2015 http://2015.caaconference.org/	Three presentations, two sessions and a workshop – over c.200 participants	CSIC, ADS, PIN, OEAW, ICS-Forth, ADS, USW
April 2015				
15-19	San Francisco, USA	SAA 2015	Presentation "ADS 3D Viewer: an example of open 3D real-time visualization system in archaeology" to c. 50 SAA members	ADS
21	Amersfoort, The Netherlands	National Conference: Digital Archaeology	Presenting ARIADNE and the Data Seal of Approval (trusted digital repository) – 40 Dutch archaeologists	KNAW-DANS
May 2015				
3	Rome, Italy	E-RIHS, European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science	Presentation of the ARIADNE project	PIN
8-10	Alun, Romania	The national symposium from Valea Alunului - 2nd edition	Archeological site or historical landscape - theory and practice in field archaeological research meeting – c. 200 attendees.	ARHEO
13	Dublin, Ireland	Awareness raising exercise with politicians (TD & Senators) of Ireland	Private meeting	DISC
13-15	Athens, Greece	Ninth IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS 2015) http://www.rcis-conf.com/rcis2015/	Paper: Automatic Process Model Discovery from Textual Methodologies: An Archaeology Case Study	CSIC

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15	Lecce, Italy	Participation in the conference: Identità Digitale Unica	Presentation of the ARIADNE project	PIN
20	Nuremberg, Germany	CIDOC CRM SIG	Presentation of the CRMarchaeo model	PIN
21-22	Aarhus, Denmark	Digital Heritage Conference 2015	Presentation "From research archives to webbased visualization: the ADS 3D viewer" to c. 120 attendees	ADS
25-27	Valparaíso, Chile	5° Seminario Internacional de Patrimonio Cultural Inmaterial: Informática Cultural, http://www.infocultura.cl	Keynote "Humanidades digitales, tecnologías semánticas, y co-investigación en patrimonio cultural" to c. 150 attendees	CSIC
June 2015				
11-12	Deva, Romania	Annual session - 135 years from establishing the history and archaeology society of Hunedoara's county.	Scientific communications	ARHEO
26	Dublin, Ireland	Irish Archaeological Data: Towards a framework: http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13614576.2015.1113037	Presentation of ARIADNE & Irish archaeology data strategies to c. 300 attendees	Discovery?
July 2015				
8	York, UK	Digital Heritage Workshop 2015	Presentation: "3D Web-Based Dynamic Platforms in Archaeology: Combining offline and online datasets to gain new understanding of the archaeological record" – c. 40 attendees	ADS

14	London, UK	ISKO-UK biennial conference http://www.iskouk.org/conference/isko-uk-conference-2015-knowledge-organisation-making-difference	Presentation paper on vocabulary mapping and linked data	USW
20-21	London, UK	Linked Pasts http://pelagios-project.blogspot.co.uk/2015/03/linked-pasts.html	Overview of ARIADNE project and work with Linked Data a Vocabularies to c. 75 attendees	ADS, USW
September 2015				
2	Nuremberg, Germany	CIDOC CRM Special Interest Group meeting	Martin Doerr presented CIDOC CRM Family, Harmonized models for the Digital World: CIDOC CRM and extensions	FORTH
2-5	Glasgow, UK	EAA 2015 Conference http://eaaglasgow2015.com/	Presentation of paper "The value of complementarity. Integrating traditional and modern ways in archaeological remote sensing"	ARUP_CAS
2-5	Glasgow, UK	EAA Conference http://eaaglasgow2015.com/	Two presentations: 1. sharing and reuse of spatial data within archaeology & Cultural Heritage 2. Standards for 3D documentation in archaeology	DISC, PIN
8-11	Rome, Italy	Reconstruction of the Archaeological Landscape through Virtual Reality: http://archeologiavirtuale.it/	Training on ARIADNE Landscape Services – 21 students	CNR ITABC
9-11	Santiago de Compostela, Spain	AARG Conference http://aarg2015.incipit.csic.es/	Presentation of ARIADNE and its relevance to remote sensing Data to c.100 attendees. Presentation of paper "Making hidden components of past landscapes interpretable: from	DISC & ZRC-SAZU & ARUP-CAS

			air photos to structured records" (ARUP-CAS)	
17	Poznan, Poland	Workshop on Extending, Mapping and Focusing CRM, TDPL2015 http://tpdl2015.info/works-hops-list/workshop-extending-mapping-focusing-crm/	Presentation of new extensions of CIDOC CRM developed within the project	PIN, FORTH
18	Poznan, Poland	14th European Networked Knowledge Organization Systems (NKOS) Workshop http://tpdl2015.info/works-hops-list/workshop-networked-knowledge-organisation-systems-services-nkos/	4 presentations directly relevant to ARIADNE (USW on mapping work, PIN on CRM time modeling, DAI on mapping, PeriodO used for periods in ARIADNE (by one of their team)	USW, PIN, DAI
25	York, UK	YorkNight European Researchers Night	Demonstration of 3DHOP at European Researchers' Night. A mega event which aims to show that research is fun and influences daily life for all of us.	ADS
28 2	Granada, Spain	Int. Conf. Digital Heritage 2015 http://www.digitalheritage2015.org/	Presentation of papers and tutorial on 3DHOP. oster and paper: Aspöck, Edeltraud; Kopetzky, Karin; Horejs, Barbara; Bietak, Manfred; Kucera, Matthias; Neubauer, Wolfgang (2015) A Puzzle in 4D: Digital Preservation and Reconstruction of an Egyptian Palace.	CNR, OEAW
October 2015				
1-2	Lecce, Italy	Workshop on "L'integrazione dei dati archeologici digitali. Esperienze e prospettive in Italia"	Presentation papers: "Il registry di ARIADNE e il modello di metadati" and ARIADNE activities and achievements	CNR-ISTI PIN

2-3	Timisoara, Romania	International Colloquium Communication And Culture Within Romance Space – 4th edition – Personalities, Phenomena and Moments in the Evolution of Romance Space, http://ciccre.weebly.com/all-for-papers.html	http://www.arheovest.com/pdf/brosura_ciccre.pdf , http://www.arheovest.com/pdf/program_ciccre.pdf	ARHEO
5-7	Madrid, Spain	Segundo Congreso Internacional de la Sociedad de Humanidades Digitales Hispánicas (HDH 2015)	Papers "A Modelling Language for Discourse Analysis in Humanities: Definition, Design, Validation and First Experiences", "Teaching Conceptual Modelling in Humanities and Social Sciences"	CSIC
14	Rome, Italy	IV Convegno di studi SITAR	Presentation of ARIADNE project to Italian archaeologist community	MiBACT-ICCU
21-22	Benevento (Italy)	Int. Conf. "Metrology for Archaeology 2015" http://vcg.isti.cnr.it/Publications/2015/MBPCDS15/	Presentation of a scientific paper	CNR
29	The Hague, the Netherlands	Training on how to deposit your data at DANS	Presented ARIADNE infrastructure to these 8 researchers	KNAW-DANS
November 2015				
4-6	Florence (Italy)	7th Round Table on polychromy in ancient sculpture and architecture	Presentation of a scientific paper	CNR
10	Umeå, Sweden	CAA-SE 2015	Presentation of a paper where ARIADNE was one of the topics.	SND

26	Zwolle, Netherlands	Reuwendagen: http://www.reuwendagen.nl/programma_donderdag_26_november.html	Presentation of ARIADNE in Session: Malta voorbij: nieuwe ontwikkelingen en initiatieven in Europa Hella Hollander (DANS): Van je eigen achtertuin naar die van de bureu. 600 attendees.	KNAW-DANS
26	Oxford, UK	CIDOC CRM SIG meeting	Discussion on CRMarchaeo, CRMsci, CRMinf and CRMba	FORTH, PIN
28	Timisoara, Romania	ArheoVest Symposium - Interdisciplinarity in Archaeology and History - third edition http://arheovest.com/symposium/arheovest_3.html	Presentations and papers on different eras and domains of research related to the archaeology field and ARIADNE to 200 attendees.	ARHEO
December 2015				
1-2	Buenos Aires (Argentina)	Workshop on "Science and innovation for the study and conservation of works of art"	Presentation of CNR-ISTI activity on ICT & CH, including ARIADNE (invited talk)	CNR
15-16	Rome, Italy	Modelli Matematici Nella Conservazione E Valorizzazione Dei Beni Culturali	Workshop organized by the Italian Academy "Accademia dei Lincei", R. Scopigno invited to present activities on Visual data and CH	CNR
16	Dublin, Ireland	ARIADNE 2015	Update of ARIADNE Activities to DARIAH Ireland Group	DISC
January 2016				
8	San Francisco, California	AIA annual meetings (congress)	Participation in seminar on open data in archaeology	AIAC
19	Vienna, OEAW	ARIADNE Data management workshop	Data management workshop	UoY-ADS, OEAW, PIN

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21	Ljubljana, ZRC-SAZU	ARIADNE Data management workshop	Data management workshop	UoY-ADS, ZRC-SAZU, PIN
21	Budapest, Hungary	The Preservation and Re-use of Archaeological Data, Central European University	Masterclasses on "Integrated Utilization of Advanced Technology in Archaeology and Heritage Preservation Today"	UoY-ADS
28	Sofia, Bulgaria	Annual Report on ARIADNE Project to the General Assembly of NIAM-BAS	Description and work done	NIAM-BAS
28	Budapest, Hungary	Gyula Forster National Centre for Cultural Heritage Management	ARIADNE introduction to the head of the registry office	MNM-NOK
February 2016				
2-3	Mexico City, Mexico	"Estudio, conservación y restauración del patrimonio cultural y arqueológico: tecnologías e infraestructuras para la investigación en Ciencia del Patrimonio"	Presentation of ARIADNE project: "El Componente Digital de las Infraestructuras de Investigación sobre el Patrimonio"	PIN
11	Llandudno, Wales, UK	3D Data: Access and Reuse	Presentation on aspects of 3D data access including information on 3DHOP viewer and ariadne portal	DISC
March 2016				
5	Lyubimets, Bulgaria	Conference "The voice of the rock"	Reported on ARIADNE project activities	NIAM-BAS
17	Rome, Italy	RAC 2016 conference http://romansocietyrac.ac.uk/rac-2016/	Discussant: presentation of Fasti Survey and discussion of Open data in survey archaeology	AIAC
18	Brighton, UK	EAC European Archaeological Council	Paper: "Saving Treasures: The DANS digital archive"	KNAW-DANS
25	Podgorica, Montenegro	Seminar within the Montenegro Katuns project at Historical Institute of Montenegro	Seminar at Podgorica University	CNR ITABC

29-2	Oslo, Norway	CAA 2016 http://2016.caaconference.org/	Session "Supporting researchers in the use and re-use of archaeological data" (UoY-ADS, PIN) Session "Archaeological Information Languages and Notations" (CSIC) Conference papers (CSIC, CNR, Athena RC, FORTH)	UoY-ADS, PIN, Athena RC, SND, KNAW-DANS, AIAC, CNR, CSIC, FORTH
29-4	Orlando, USA	SAA Conference (http://www.saa.org/):	Symposium: What do we mean by "Digital Curation?" (ADS) Paper: Current Developments in CyberInfrastructure in European Archaeology(ADS & PIN) Paper: Building a European Data Infrastructure for Archaeology (ADS)	UoY-ADS, PIN
April 2016				
7	Sharjah, UAE	ATHAR/ICCROM conference on culture	Presentation on ARIADNE and FASTI Conservation	AIAC
14	Timisoara, Romania	Exhibition - DACII DE LA MUNTE, DACII DE LA CAMPIE - https://www.facebook.com/events/213495965694770/	discussion about the evolution of the ARIADNE project and its results	ARHEO
15-17	Durham, UK	Durham Conference 2016 (http://community.dur.ac.uk/j.c.chapman/tripillia/conference/)	Paper: Medieval mega-sites in Bohemia (Martin Kuna)	ARUP_CAS
18-22	Timisoara, Romania	The "other" school: archaeological activities with school children	Activities with school children, discussion about the European context and the importance of archaeological research	ARHEO
19	Munich, Germany	Seminar at the University of Munich	Seminar at the University, presenting and discussing Fasti Online	AIAC

27	Pisa, Italy	Giorno della solidarieta' 2016 - Dissemination event to high schools	R. Scopigno and M. Callieri (CNR_ISTI) presented ARIADNE technologies to an event concerning the theme "Archaeology: how to document and restore war destructions?"	CNR_ISTI
28	Vienna, Austria	Workshop 'Old Excavation Data - what can we do?' http://www.orea.oeaw.ac.at/fileadmin/user_upload/veranstaltungen/2016/Workshops_ICAANE/Old_excavation_data_%E2%80%93_What_can_we_do.pdf	Workshop with presentations and discussions of projects on digitization and archiving of excavation data	OEAW
May 2016				
4	Budapest, Hungary	Workshop - Hungarian National Museum Archaeology Database: structure, content, relation to ARIADNE	Introducing ARIADNE Portal and the HNM Archaeology Database to archaeologists	MNM-NOK
23	Hungary	Introducing ARIADNE to the Hungarian Excavation Committee	Presentation on the aims and structure/working principles of the Hungarian Archaeology Database and the ARIADNE Portal	MNM-NOK
27	Stara Zagoro, Bulgaria	LV National archaeological conference	Presentation about the Archaeological map of Bulgaria	NIAM-BAS
30-1	Velké Pavlovice, Czech Republic	Computer Application in Archaeology 2016 (http://www.phil.muni.cz/waoa/home/ppa2016)	Conference papers by Martin Gojda, Lucie Culikova, Martin Kuna, Dana Krivankova	ARUP_CAS
June 2016				
1-3	Grenoble, France	Tenth IEEE International Conference on Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS 2016) http://rcis-conf.com/rcis2016/	Paper: Using Model Views to Assist with Model Conformance and Extension	CSIC
23-25	Fano, Italy	Landscape and Archaeology UNISCAPE http://www.centrostudivitr	Keynote presentation at the conference (Sofia Pescarin)	CNR-ISTI

		uviani.org/programme/		
28	Hungary	European Union Projects' Information Day	Presentation on the aims and structure/working principles of the Hungarian Archaeology Database and the ARIADNE Portal	NMN-NOK
July 2016				
1	Uppsala, Sweden	ARKDIS Conference	Keynote paper by Julian Richards, including presentation of European interoperability initiatives	UoY-ADS
7-8	Salerno/ Napoli, Italy	Project DATABENC - CHIS: Cultural Heritage Information System, funded by Campania Region	International Advisory Board Meeting (F. Niccolucci and R. Scopigno are members of the Board)	PIN, CNR
11-12	Krakow, Poland	Seventh International Workshop on Computational Models of Narrative (http://narrative.csail.mit.edu/cm16/)	Presentation of the paper: Steps Towards a Formal Ontology of Narratives Based on Narratology. Valentina Bartalesi, Carlo Meghini and Daniele Metilli	CNR ISTI
August 2016				
28-29	Kyoto, Japan	WAC8 conference (http://wac8.org)	Paper by Edeltraud Aspöck, Digitizing Early Farming Cultures: sharing data on Neolithic sites and finds in Greece and Anatolia	OEAW
31-9	Vilnius, Lithuania	EAA Conference (http://eaavilnius2016.lt/):	Session: Open Access and Open Data in Archaeology: Following the ARIADNE thread Papers (ADS, AIAC, Athena RC, Salzburg Research)	ADS, PIN, AIAC, Athena RC, Salzburg Research
31-2	Prague, Czech Republic	Central European Conference of Historical Geographers (http://www.historickageografie.cz/cechg2016)	Invited paper (M. Kuna)	ARUP_CAS

September 2016				
5-7	Valencia, Spain	ARQUEOLÓGICA 2.0 8th International Congress on Archaeology, Computer Graphics, Cultural Heritage and Innovation http://arqueologica8.webs.upv.es/	Presentation of poster (S. Stuhec, E. Aspoeck, A. Masur, P. Andorfer, K. Zaytseva): Putting 3d models into context – the schachermeyr pottery collection and the defc app.	OEAW
7-9	Pilsen, Czech Republic	AARG Conference 2016 https://sites.google.com/site/aargpilsen2016/	Presentation of papers (M. Kuna, M. Gojda, L. Culikova), organizing of the conference	ARUP_CAS
26-27	Nanterre, France	Archivage, publication et mise à disposition de données archéologiques, MASA Consortium (Mémoires des Archéologues et des Sites Archéologiques). https://masa2016.sciencesconf.org/	Presentation (Julian Richards and Federico Nurra) “Digital Preservation and Access in a European Perspective: introducing ARIADNE	ADS INRAP
29-30	Weimar, Germany	Das digitale und die denkmalpflege	Invited presentation by Roberto Scopigno on “3D digitization efforts and technology development in Italy”	CNR ISTI
October 2016				
27-30	Paestum, Italy			CNR ITABAC
November 2016				
16-11	Vienna, Austria	CHNT 2016 - 21th International Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies	ARIADNE session “Preservation as a foundation for the reuse of data” and Roundtable “Where is an archive for my data?”	Session: ADS, KNAW-DANS, DAI/IANUS; roundtable: ÖAW-OREA and SRFG
26	Timisoara, Romania	ArheoVest Symposium - Interdisciplinary in History and Archaeology	Presentation	ARHEOVEST

December 2016				
5	Budapest, Hungary	Digitális régészet - A Magyar emzeti Múzeum Adatbázisa (Digital archaeology - The Hungarian National Museum Archaeology Database)	Presentation about the HMN database	HMN
8-10	Sofia, Bulgaria	A workshop for Archaeological map of Bulgaria (http://naim.bg/en/content/news/600/857/703/)	Presentation about ARIADNE	NIAM-BAS
9	Sofia, Bulgaria	"А сега накъде" - broadcast on the Bulgarian National Radio http://bnr.bg/hristobotev/post/100769355	Materials for ARIADNE project on the Bulgarian National Radio, an interview with Assoc. Prof. Dr. Lyudmil Vagalinski	NIAM-BAS
10	Cork, Ireland	Virtual Heritage Network (Ireland) Conference	Paper by Evie Monaghan & Rónán Swan: 'Collaboration in Digitising Cultural Heritage: Transport Infrastructure Ireland's Heritage Collection and the wider European Context'	Discovery
12-14	Prato, Italy	ARIADNE winter school	Presentations	PIN, ICS-FORTH
14	Prato, Italy	PARTHENOS symposium	Networking	PIN, UoY-ADS, CNR-ISTI, Athena RC
15-16	Florence, Italy	ARIADNE conference: Unlocking the potential of digital archaeological data: http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events/ARIADNE-Final-Conference	Presentations	PIN, UoY-ADS, Saltzberg, CNR-ISTI, Athena RC, OEAW, INRAP, all partners
22	Sofia, Bulgaria	http://www.afish.bg/news/item/2389-digitalna-nishkana-ariadne-vodi-ucheni-iz-labirinta-na-arheologiyata.html	Article in an online newsletter	NIAM-BAS